

Gendering the Academy
and Research: combating
Career Instability and Asymmetries

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16

Selection of measures for integrating gender into research and curricula in six European countries

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document compiles reports on the measures that the beneficiary organisations (project partners) have taken in order to advance integration of gender perspective in research and teaching. The objective of this task was to increase the awareness of the importance of integrating a gender perspective in research and students' curricula in academia. Though aiming towards common goal, project partners had quite different strategies in conducting this task due to 1) different institutional settings in each of the partner institutions, and 2) estimation of different needs among scientists coming from different field of study. In order to reflect the common objective, and allow basic comparability, the reports have been organised in a similar way: first, presenting the institutional setting and existent practices in integration of gender into the content of research and curricula, then, describing different actions each partner took and providing rationale for chosen strategies, and finally, noting challenges faced in the process of organising and conducting particular activity and reflecting on lessons learned. In **General Introduction**, the editor provides short overview of commonalities and differences among the actions taken by different partners, as well as in challenges they faced. After finding how each partner faced these challenges in a different way, it concludes with the necessity for tailor-made measures. The report of the **Italian** partner describes how they organised separate activities in two test departments and on the level of the whole University. In the STEM department (dedicated to information engineering and computer science) they commission an expert organisation specialised in connecting gender to ICT. In the SSH department (dedicated to social research) they organised optional teaching activity, while at the level of the University of Trento the team participated in creating a cycle of seminars on gender offered to all scientific departments. The **Belgian** partner organised a separate workshop for each of the test departments in cooperation with newly appointed rector's councillor on gender issues. Learning from mixed success, the report offers very concrete recommendations for potential future steps and activities. The **Dutch** partner faced challenges because of which a specialised training on integrating gender perspective was not a viable option in either of the test departments. In the STEM department (dealing with mathematics and physics) integration of gender into content of research was substituted with activities relating to gender in curricula, due to inability to connect topics of gender and the topics the department deals with. On the other hand, the content of gender is present in the research of the department to such a level that the SSH department (of management research) did not need a specialised training. Instead the team developed a set of new academic courses dedicated to gender within the school of management. The **Icelandic** partner fitted the training into already well developed institutional setting at the University of Iceland, and organised a joint workshop for academic and support staff. The **Swiss** partner also employed the existing institutional mechanisms and build on previous initiatives related to integrating gender perspective into research of the SSH department, while they focused on helping such mechanisms within the STEM department. Finally, the **Slovenian** team organised workshops in the two test departments based on the Toolkit for Integrating Gender-Sensitive Approach into research and Teaching, since they had virtually no previous experience in integrating gender perspective into the core research.

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GENERAL INTRODUCTION

One of the objectives of the GARCIA project is to enhance integration of gender perspective in research and teaching among the project partners, especially in the two test departments in each of the countries involved (Italy, Belgium, the Netherlands, Iceland, Switzerland and Slovenia). The same goal was fulfilled in different ways depending on different institutional settings in each partner institution, and different needs of the specific test departments, half of which fall under STEM (science, technology, engineering, and mathematics) and another half SSH (social sciences and humanities). This document compiles reports on the measures that GARCIA project partners have taken in order to meet this aim – strategies that include trainings and workshops for academic and support staff on how to incorporate gender perspective into research; creation of new syllabus and academic programmes dedicated to gender dimension within particular discipline; developing and enhancing research networks on gender-related topics; fostering inclusion of gender into institutional strategies of the Universities; and even popularising gender perspective in academia through cultural festivals. Most project partners strove to incorporate the measure taken into already existing initiatives at their institutions, which promises increased sustainability of this activity even after the end of GARCIA project. There was a large discrepancy among the specific test departments ranging from those with well-established gender-related research portfolios to those where inclusion of gender into the research and teaching was completely unknown issue. However, some common challenges were faced by virtually all the project partners. In cases where specialised training/workshop was organised, the attendance rate was often low: either because the invited researchers consider themselves experts in gender field, so they believe they do not need such a training; or because they come from such scientific field (usually STEM) that they do not see relevance of gender for their own research. Since STEM researchers find particularly challenging to understand how gender is relevant for their research, it proved most fruitful to design the workshops based on practical examples from their own field. Therefore, it seems crucial to have a sensitised trainer that is an expert in particular scientific field to which attendants belong. Strategy for the future should be to find a suitable trainer for this kind of workshops and bring her/him to the faculty department instead of having an in-house gender expert. In case of SSH departments, several project partners noted that instead of organising an ad hoc workshop on integrating gender perspective into the research, this issue should be tackled as part of obligatory professional training for young academics that otherwise usually involve topics like teaching skills, public speaking and funding opportunities. In few cases project partners faced resistance in the form of lack of interest and genuine support on the part of the head of the departments, which only demonstrates to what extent institutional support is indispensable for the systematic integration of gender perspective into the academic conduct. In order to reflect the common objective put before all the partners, and allow basic comparability, the reports have been organised in a similar way: first, presenting the institutional setting and existent practices in integration of gender into the content of research and curricula, then, describing different actions each partner took and providing rationale for chosen strategies, and finally, noting challenges faced in the process of organising and conducting particular activity, as well as reflecting on lessons learned and providing concrete recommendations for future steps.

1. ITALY

By Francesca Fiore, Rossella Bozzon, Annalisa Murgia & Barbara Poggio

1.1 Introduction

This chapter describes the actions implemented by the GARCIA team at the University of Trento with the aim to foster the integration of a gender-sensitive approach into teaching and research activities. The chapter is organised in three main paragraphs. The first two report the activities developed in the two departments involved in the GARCIA project, while the last paragraph summarises the activities focussed on gender issues developed at the university level.

According to the needs emerged from the analyses of the data collected over the first period of the project, we have diversified the activities implemented in the two beneficiary departments.

In the case of the Department of Information Engineering and Computer Science (DISI), in line with its hectic activities focused on the development of new research projects – in which graduate students, PhD students and postdoctoral research fellows are often involved – we decided to organized a training course devoted to foster the inclusion of a gender sensitive approach in their research activities. This training course was entrusted to Yellow Window, an agency specialised in the implementation of gender-sensitive methodology in research, which arranged a course shaped on the main research interests/topics of the DISI department.

In the case of the Department of Sociology and Social Research (DSRS), given the presence of a wide range of on-going research projects adopting a gender approach, we decided to support mainly teaching activities. More precisely, we collaborated to the organization of the course “Il genere nella società contemporanea” [Gender in contemporary societies] of the undergraduate degree in “Sociology” providing an integrative teaching activity, a methodological laboratory targeted to undergraduate students on how to conduct a research adopting a gender sensitive approach.

Finally, at the university level, the GARCIA project actively promoted the integration of a gender approach taking part to the organisation of three events: 1) the researchers’ Night 2015; 2) a cycle of interdepartmental seminars on gender issues for students on bachelor and master degree courses, developed jointly with the Centro Studi Interdisciplinari di Genere (Interdisciplinary Centre for Gender Studies); 3) and a film festival on gender and science.

1.2 Actions implemented in the STEM department: a training on integrating gender perspective into research

In the Department of Information Engineering and Computer Science (DISI) the GARCIA project implementd a training course on integrating gender perspective into research activities held by the experts of Yellow Window

(<http://www.yellowwindow.com/en/home>).

The decision to implement this training was led by the strong research vocation expressed by the Department, whose primary aim is to develop knowledge in the areas of the ICT (Information and Communication Technologies) adopting interdisciplinary approaches. In such context, we believe that gender perspective is a fundamental methodological tool useful to develop promising new research projects.

In organising the training, our main concern was to identify a period over the academic year not saturated by teaching and research duties in order to guarantee the participation of a consistent number of teaching and research staff. Thus, in the organizational process, we decided to include the training workshop in the *ICT Days*, a highly participated scientific event launched in 2009 as an initiative by the Department of Information Engineering and Computer Science of the University of Trento, dedicated to the broad subject of Information and Communication Technology.

Thanks to its success, the event has now become an important meeting opportunity both local and national. The *ICT Days* event includes opportunities of placement for both former and latter students, becoming an arena dedicated to the encounter between companies and university students. It also offers the possibility to compete in a hackathon, an American-type event in which various work teams compete in a software programming marathon creating, testing and validating their projects. Moreover, with an Education Day dedicated to orientation, during the *ICT Days*, prospective students are given an opportunity to interact with the academic world through direct contact with the university structure, its services, teaching staff and students (<http://2016.ictdays.it/en/about>).

Thanks to its visibility, we decided that it was a good opportunity to include our training in such a deep and alive environment, in order to involve a wider public and disseminate the project to a larger audience that could engage all the actors of the university, from the students to the researchers and professors. This is also why we established a collaboration between communication teams. With this coordination of effort we managed to have a more effective dissemination of our initiative. We in fact used different communication channels such as: the GARCIA Project social media (Facebook, Twitter), the *ICT Days* web site and social media (Facebook, Twitter) and an Eventbrite has been used for gathering the registrations. Moreover, we appeared in few press realises before and after our event. Finally, during the event a live interview have been done for a local radio (SanbaRadio). A GARCIA team member, in the radio interview explained the purpose of the workshop and, more in general, the main aim of the project.

Yellow Window invitation to the Training Workshop

1.2.1 Attendees

During the training we had 26 attendees: 18 of them were female and the other 8 male (figure 1).

More in details: 18 of the participant were Italian while the others were coming from other countries such as Spain, Slovenia, Namibia, Paraguay, Russia and Bielorrussia.

Most of them are currently working at the University of Trento but we had attendees also coming from a private research centre (FBK) and collateral research projects. They had different theoretical backgrounds, mostly from the Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) area but also someone from disciplines such as Social Sciences and Sociology (SSH) (Tab 1).

The attendees, as showed in table 2, were in different stages of their careers: the majority are finishing their PhDs (11), some others are postdocs or research fellows (10). Just few of them are already in tenured position and all of them were women.

Fig. 1 Attendees by sex

Tab 1 – Participants by field of study

Field of Studies	Sex		Total
	Female	Male	
Computer science	0	3	3
Corporate Governance	1	0	1
Design Research	2	1	3
Economics	1	0	1
Environmental Engineering	1	0	1
Human-computer interactions	3	2	4
ICT	1	0	1
Meteorology	1	0	1
Neuroscience	1	0	1
Social informatics	0	1	1
Sociology/Social sciences	4	0	4
Sociology/ICT	2	0	2
Software engineering	0	1	1
User experience	1	0	1
Total	18	8	26

Tab 2 – Participants by research positions

Research position	Sex		Total
	Female	Male	
Full professor	1	0	1
Assistant professor	1	0	1
Postdoc, research fellow	7	3	10
Co.co.co	2	0	2
PhD	6	5	11
Freelance designer	1	0	1
Total	18	8	26

1.2.2 Course materials

This training/action has been designed following the recommendation by the European Commission within FP5, FP6 and FP7, which reads: introducing a gender-sensitive approach makes research and teaching of higher quality and validity by enabling researchers to write a more competitive proposal, and it makes research results more relevant to society since gender-balanced research teams perform better and attract top-level researchers.

We needed to invite professional trainers with a consolidate experience in the research sector and with a gender sensitive approach and negotiate a training course on how to integrate a gender perspective in project proposals on STEM disciplines (in our case mainly computer science and information technology). In order to do so, following the advises received by colleagues involved in other European Structural Change Projects on gender in Higher Education (e.g. Stages, Trigger) we decided to contact the product/service/policy design group **Yellow Window** for leading this workshop. They define themselves as "mainstreaming design thinking throughout its three core activities: product design, service design and policy design." They "privilege user-centred approaches, mobilising methodologies that combine observation, analysis and creativity, in a genuine and permanent prospect for enhancing products and services." They have a longstanding expertise on setting up and delivering trainings specifically targeting the research community. In particular, on behalf of the European Commission, *they developed a toolkit on 'Gender in EU-funded Research'* and they organised over 70 training sessions across Europe.

The training sessions they usually organise aim at raising awareness on how to promote gender equality in scientific research and we asked them to target as specific focus the main research interests/topics of the DISI department. The main purpose of this action, in fact, was to help all the research staff from the DISI to integrate a gender-sensitive approach into their activities, but also to understand how to apply this approach when conceiving new project applications and curricula. For the motivations above, we thought that Yellow Window could have the perfect fit, methods and mind-set to transmit this knowledge to the DISI audience.

Moreover, in line with the strong focus of this department on the development of new research projects – in which graduate students, PhD students and postdoctoral research fellows even with different academic backgrounds are often involved – we asked to mainly focus on the implementation of activities devoted to include a gender sensitive approach.

The title was "**Training workshop: integrating a gender perspective in research**". The training was designed to give to the research community practical tools to integrate gender aspects into research. This one-day interactive workshop addressed topics such as promoting equal opportunities for women and men in research teams (including in decision-making positions) and integrating a gender dimension in research and innovation. The trainers developed both topics as contribution to excellence in research and as highly valuable in Horizon 2020 calls. The training had been delivered in English.

Picture shoot from the GARCIA team during the workshop.

The trainers were Catarina Arnout and Maxime Forest.

Catarina Arnout holds an MSc in Services Management and a bachelor degree in Psychology (Clinical and Health Psychology). She is a consultant and gender expert at Yellow Window since 2011. Catarina conducts applied research mainly focussing on gender issues. Catarina was a team member of Yellow Window's project 'Toolkit and Training: Gender in EU-funded Research' (2009-2012). Yellow Window sets up trainings aiming at integrating a gender dimension in research. Catarina is a trainer and she is also responsible for liaising with interested parties to organise these trainings.

Maxime Forest holds a PhD in Political Sciences and a Master in Comparative Political Analysis. Since January 2012, he has been collaborating with Yellow Window as senior researcher, consultant and gender trainer. Since 2013, he is associate researcher and senior lecturer in gender politics at Sciences Po Paris, where he was appointed Scientific Coordinator of the EU-funded structural change project EGERA (Effective Gender Equality in Research and the Academia). Maxime was a gender trainer of Yellow Window's project 'Toolkit and Training: Gender in EU-funded Research'. Although this project ended in 2012, Maxime continues delivering trainings on this topic on behalf of Yellow Window.

The main objectives of the training were:

- Strengthening participants' basic knowledge on gender issues;
- Raising participants' awareness on the importance of integrating gender in research ;
- Informing participants on gender in H2020 ;
- Strengthening participants' capacities to integrate gender in research.

Thus, following the objectives, during the morning a general introduction to gender in research had been provided, while in the afternoon the focus of the work more on practical exercises specifically on ICT research.

More in details, the trainers opened the morning session introducing the basic concepts. As an ice breaker in order to connect with the attendees, in fact, the trainers asked two male participants to draw a female body and two female participants to draw a male body.

Pictures taken during the workshop.

Starting from the figure, then together with the group, they delineate, what could be defined as a peculiarity of “sex” and what of “gender”. From these basic definitions it was then easier to approach the concept of stereotypes and to better understand if inequalities might have a cost.

“A topic is considered gender relevant when it and/or its findings affect individuals of groups of persons. In these cases, gender issues should be integrated at various stages of the action and when relevant, specific studies can be included.” (Horizon 2020 Work Programme 2014-2015, General Introduction)

They reconnected to the H2020 objectives such as fostering gender balance in Horizon 2020 research teams, ensuring gender balance in decision-making and integrating gender/sex analysis in R&I.

Figure from the Yellow Window presentation.

At the end of the discussion, the trainers gave to the attendees a concrete instrument to analyse gender sensibility in the different stages of a project. The trainers guided the attendees in the construction of the gender sensitive cycle, reflecting together on the different variables that could be taken into account.

Picture taken during the workshop: the trainers draw the gender-sensitive research cycle with the collaboration of all the attendees.

This led to the afternoon discussion where, using the gender-sensitive research cycle as a tool, in groups the attendees analysed concrete research projects already granted from the European Commission. They had to examine the presented cases with a gender-sensitive methodology, understanding when and where gender was or was not considered in the different stages of the project. This was an exercise to understand how a research project that does not apply a gender-sensitive approach may lead to general conclusion based on partial data.

Figure from the Yellow Window presentation.

1.2.3 Existing Practices

Before the training, the participants received a brief questionnaire via email. We sent it to the contact list we had from the list of participants of the Eventbrite. We wanted to have an overview of the existing practices before the workshop and to better know our audience. We had all the attendees to sign a privacy realise for the use of their data in an aggregated way, so anonymously.

We started asking some basic questions about the attendee such as gender, field of studies and Academic position (postdoc, assistant professor, associate professor, full professor, etc.) (<https://docs.google.com/a/unitn.it/forms/d/1oLzpgzhMEBteahSH9cTS-qMefDcNZLCFTWjEQwCZAsE/viewform?c=0&w=1>).

Then, in the survey, we asked the following questions :

- Do you find yourself to be gender-sensitive in your research?
- Thus far, have you integrated gender in any of your research projects?
- Have ever used gender-sensitive methodology?

In the possible answers we considered were “Yes”, “No” and “I don’t know”.

The outcome for the first question made us understands how most of our female audience (11) was already gender-sensitive. A big part of them, anyway, had never really thought about it before and we can tell it from the high percentage of “I don’t know” (6). For the male participants, part of them (3) declared to be gender sensitive while 4 of them said not to be at all (Tab. 3).

Tab 3 – Do you find yourself to be gender sensitive in your research?

	Sex		Total
	Female	Male	
Yes	11	3	14
No	1	4	5
I do not know	6	1	7
Total	18	8	26

Even if many of them have a gender-sensitive approach more than half had never applied this sensibility to any of their researches, so far. The ones who had any experience of it were all women (9 out 10) (Fig 4).

Tab 4 –Thus far, have you integrated gender in any of your research projects?

	Sex		Total
	Female	Male	
Yes	9	1	10
No	7	7	14
I do not know	2	0	2
Total	18	8	26

Finally only 5 (4 women and 1 man) declared to have used a gender-sensitive methodology in their research while 7 trainee are not aware about it (I do not know). Almost all men (6 out 8) declared that they have never used this methodology (tab. 5).

Tab 5 – Have you ever used gender sensitive methodology?

	Sex		Total
	Female	Male	
Yes	4	1	5
No	8	6	14
I do not know	6	1	7
Total	18	8	26

Picture taken during the workshop.

1.2.4 Noted challenges

During the workshop, overall, we have not noticed open resistances. The participants did not express reservation regarding suggestions for gender-sensitive approach throughout the training. Just one of the attendees looked concerned about the presented topics.

The atmosphere was indeed cooperative and this feeling was also underlined by the positive feedbacks given in the exit questionnaire.

Most participants did find hard to recognise the relation between gender and the main topic of their research. Belonging to a STEM environment, indeed, most of the female participants started to look at their research group dynamic from a more critical point of

view, not considered much till then. Being surrounded by man, they said, many of the issues about gender and equality are not even taken into consideration as existing problems.

What are the main/most interesting points that you learned in this training?

- FACTS ABOUT GENDER INEQUALITY IN MANY ASPECTS OF LIFE
- GENDER REALLY MATTERS! IT'S NOT JUST MY PERCEPTION.

Answer given by a female participant in the exit questionnaire.

In the morning, indeed, some perplexities emerged when the trainers were explaining how theoretically gender could be included in a research project. In particular, those who do theoretical research were more distressed than those who come from applied disciplines.

In the afternoon session, however, when in small group they tried to apply the given suggestions to existing projects, many of them realised how to apply the concepts discussed in the previous part.

The exercises they had to do have been decisive in order to let them understand the possible discrepancy between theory and practice in research.

In particular, the gender sensitive cycle has given the method: it was helpful to understand how to read the stages of research and what questions you should ask yourself if you want to introduce a gender sensitive approach. The afternoon, then, led not only to apply the methodology learned, but also to criticize it.

In one of the discussion started from the analysis of criticisms of this methodology, one comments raised by a male attendees was really interesting. He was underling the ambivalences of action on gender inequalities and the risk of reinforcing stereotypes. In his opinion, reported also in the exit questionnaire, reinforcing too much on the idea that actions for women has to be done and developed in order to reach equality, could not break down/solve an asymmetry, but create new ones. This comment was a starting point to discuss about gender as a relational concept, not only connected with sex and individuals, but with the acknowledgement of power relations and diversities within cultures, included the academic culture and the different research approaches.

If relevant, what are the issues addressed in the training you still feel less confident about?

Focusing too much on "gender" maintains the existing discrimination between men and women and it might be against equality.

Answer given by a male participant in the exit questionnaire

1.2.5 Evaluation

After the training we asked the attendees to fill an exit questionnaire, quite long and extensive (see Annex 1). We merged some questions from Yellow Window as evaluation of the training itself and some questions useful for us in term of evaluation of the

effectiveness of the action we designed.

Our questions, specifically, were the following:

- To what extent you find gender relevant for your research?
- Did this workshop change your perspective on that? If yes, how?
- To what extent do you find suggestions for gender-sensitive approach applicable to your work?
- Is it feasible that you would apply these suggestions in one of your next research projects?

Copy of the full questionnaire is reported in the Appendix 1 .

The outcomes of this survey are aligned with the results of the previous researches conducted during the first parts of the GARCIA project and the discussion occurred within the group during the workshop.

It has been underlined how the lack of recognition of the relevance of gender in research and teaching is closely related to the underrepresentation of women at all levels of academic and scientific careers (particularly on the highest positions). Because of that the integration of gender-sensitive approach is going hand in hand with a better inclusion of women in research and teaching. Due to the underrepresentation, however, equality in many contexts is not perceived as an issue that needs to be considered by the research team. As well as gender.

As we can see from some given answer, because of the lack of consideration for the gender dimension and the different relations of power, many times the gender dimension is left behind.

What could prevent you from using the acquired knowledge in your work? OPPOSITION BY MORE POWERFUL PEOPLE IN ACADEMY
What could prevent you from using the acquired knowledge in your work? GENDER UNSENSITIVE, IGNORANT INDIVIDUALS

Answer given by a 2 female participants in the exit questionnaire

Moreover, talking to the group in the conclusion of the workshop, we had a confirmation of how the gender imbalance in research/teaching staff is often connected to the allocation of resources in academia: STEM projects proved to be more often led by male researchers. And this is one of the reason why in many situations the relation of power does not allow to change existing projects adding new approaches.

Overall, the general feeling about the training was positive. The expected outcome of having future development of new research projects of our attendees with a gender-

sensitive approach has been accomplished, as they stated in the questionnaires. Most of them considered also the inclusion of gender-sensitive practices in the on-going research projects (and teaching).

Finally, we strongly believe that, learning practical tools to integrate gender aspects into research and to promote equal opportunities for women and men in research teams (including in decision-making positions), will improve excellence in research. Moreover, since these aspects are highly valued in Horizon 2020 calls, we hope that this institutional support will encourage the use of gender perspective in the proposed research projects, making future project proposals more competitive at the European level.

1.3 Actions implemented in the SSH department: a course on integrating gender perspective into teaching

In the Department of Sociology and Social Research, the GARCIA project implemented a 24 hours Research Laboratory titled “Gender differences in students' experiences” focussed on how to integrate a gender-sensitive approach in social research, applied to the study of the transition from school to work.

The GARCIA Research Laboratory was a supplementary (optional) teaching activity offered to the students attending the course “Il genere nella società contemporanea” [Gender issues in the contemporary society], which was introduced among the optional teaching courses of the undergraduate course in “Sociology” in the academic year 2015/16. The active attendance of the 75% of the Laboratory allowed the students to increase the final evaluation obtained at the end of the course by two point (out of 30).

Both the course and the laboratory were conducted by members of the Italian team of the GARCIA Project. The teacher of the course was Francesca Sartori, while the tutors of the research laboratory were Rossella Bozzon and Annalisa Murgia.

The contents and the research activities included in the Research Laboratory were discussed and agreed with Francesca Sartori and the laboratory was approved by the Head of the Department.

The program of the laboratory was included in the Syllabus of the course available on the department website (https://www.esse3.unitn.it/Guide/PaginaADContest.do?jsessionid=5B9A212FBA3F0396B0EBACC2FC32B083.esse3-unitn-prod-02?cod_lingua=eng&ad_cont_id=10137*92324*2015*2008*9999).

Finally, the course and the research laboratory were promoted by the Department offices with an email sent to all the undergraduate students of the Faculty of Sociology.

1.3.1 Course materials

As explained in the Syllabus, the main objective of the course “Il genere nella società contemporanea” [Gender issues in the contemporary society] was to transmit to

students the ability to analyse and understand the social phenomena that make gender a basic explanatory variable. A second aim was to gain the ability to reflect and understand the meanings of gender and to create awareness of its effects on individual life and more specifically on guidelines, choices, planning and social rules.

The course examined the concept of gender as it has evolved, using various theoretical approaches to highlight its centrality in explaining some social inequalities in different contexts. Lectures and discussion concerned: 1) Sex and gender: concepts and theoretical approaches; 2) The specificity of gender, men and women in contemporary culture: roles, images, stereotypes; 3) The history of women's movements and feminism; 4) Socialization according to a gender perspective; 5) Gender and educational processes; 6) Gender and labour market; 7) Family: inequality in the division of domestic work and care and the parental roles; 8) The politics and women's discrimination. The teaching methods were lectures and group works. The verification of learning evaluation was based on an individual research paper of 15 pages on a topic agreed upon with the professor.

In parallel to the standard course, the **Research Laboratory titled "Gender differences in students' experiences"** offered to the students a practical training on the construction of a research design, together with competences in data collection and in the analysis of quantitative and qualitative data. The activities were mainly focused on methodological issues related to:

- 1) How to elaborate a gender-sensitive interview guide and conduct qualitative interviews;
- 2) How to elaborate a gender-sensitive questionnaire.

The case study developed during the Laboratory focused on the school-to-work transition and on the life/career trajectories of master students who are attending both SSH (Social Sciences and Humanities) and STEM (Science Technology Engineering Mathematics) faculties. We chose this topic because of the proximity of the attending students to these experiences and phase of life course that should have allowed to simplify the procedure of obtaining, interviewing and developing the contents included in the interview guide and in the questionnaire.

The laboratory was divided in three main parts, each of them organised in 4 lessons.

During the first part, we introduced the course and the research field offering a general overview on: 1) gender differences in higher education and in career development, 2) the statistical data and research evidences on education, labour market and young generation life courses in the Italian context. The main aim was to give general information on the main phenomena which are characterising the educational system, labour market, as well as educational, working and personal trajectories of young generations adopting a gender perspective.

In the fourth lesson, we invited 4 students of the University of Trento – 1 man and 1 woman who are attending a master course in SSH disciplines, and 1 man and 1 woman who are attending a master course in STEM – to take part to a roundtable. During this event, the invited students introduced themselves, their school and work choices and experiences, they told us about their everyday life and future prospects. The main aim of

the roundtable was to individuate topics, features that could be considered and included in an interview guide and a questionnaire developed during the Laboratory, having in mind the heterogeneity of the individual experiences.

In the second part of the Laboratory, we focused on qualitative methods in sociology and on the development of a gender-sensitive interview guide.

This part was organized in 4 lessons: a theoretical lesson on qualitative methods and on the instrument of the interview, two lessons dedicated to the elaboration of a semi-structured interview guide and one lesson dedicated to the presentation of the results of the interviews carried out by attending students with male and female master students in SSH and STEM disciplines.

The interview guide developed during the Laboratory considered 3 main areas of interests: 1) the present everyday life, 2) the educational career, 3) and the future prospects in work and personal life.

In the third part, we focused on quantitative methods in sociology and on the development of a gender-sensitive questionnaire. Also this part was organized in 4 lessons: a theoretical lesson on the research instrument of the questionnaire, and 3 applied lessons dedicated to the elaboration of a questionnaire on educational and career choices, life course transitions and future perspectives of master students. The questionnaire was developed selecting questions from two questionnaires already used in the Italian context to study the school-to-work transitions and the living conditions of young people in Italy:

- The Istat survey on “University graduates’ vocational integration” (available at: <http://www.istat.it/it/archivio/8338>)
- The IARD questionnaire on the living condition (Buzzi et al., 2007, available at: <http://www.sociologia.unimib.it/DATA/hot/1278/2011-2012%20I%20anno%20Parti%20A%20e%20B/1%20anno%202011-2012%20-%20parte%20A/es%203a%20quest%20ricerca%20iard%20giovani.pdf>)

During the applied lessons we critically reviewed the already existing questionnaires adopting a gender approach. More precisely we substantially revised the parts on socio-demographic characteristics and the social origins of the two questionnaires.

The final questionnaire schema comprises 6 main areas: the current condition, educational career, job experiences, future prospects and life course transitions, and socio demographic characteristics. We assigned to each student the task to select the questions of a specific session. Then we amalgamated each part in order to obtain a single and coherent questionnaire. In the final lesson, we critically discussed the questionnaire developed articulating its potentials and limits.

In the Annex 2a and 2b we included the materials used and developed during the Research Laboratory. All materials are in Italian. More precisely:

- **Appendix 2a** includes the interview guide developed in the second part of the Research Laboratory;
- **Appendix 2b** includes the questionnaires developed in the third part of the Research Laboratory.

Program of the Research Laboratory

First part: School to work transitions from a gender point of view

- 3 March 2016 Introduction of the course and presentation of the fieldwork.
10 March 2016: Gender differences in higher education and in career development
17 March 2016: Statistical background and some information on available data and questionnaires
4 April 2016: “Voices from the fieldwork” – Roundtable with a male and a female master students in STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics) disciplines and a male and a female master students in SSH (Social Sciences and Humanities) disciplines.

Second part: How to develop gender-sensitive qualitative research instruments: the interview guide.

- 7 April 2016: Introduction to qualitative methods: the interview
14 April 2016: Elaboration of a semi-structured interview guide
21 April 2016: Presentation and correction of the students’ interview outlines
28 April 2016: Presentation of the interviews conducted by the students and discussion on the main topic that could be included in a questionnaire.

Third part: How to develop gender-sensitive quantitative research instruments: the questionnaire.

- 5 May 2016: Introduction to quantitative methods – the questionnaire.
12 May 2016: Elaboration of a questionnaire
19 May 2016: Presentation and correction of the students’ questionnaires
26 May 2016: Test and discussion of the final questionnaires

1.3.2 Existing practices

The participants who attended and fully completed the methodological laboratory were five female students. Of these, three are attending the third year, one is attending the first year and one is a part-time student of the degree in Sociology.

For all the students, it was the first experience in a research laboratory and in a course entirely focussed on gender topics. In the past, some of them attended some seminars and events organised by the Interdisciplinary Centre of Gender Studies of the University of Trento. In that occasions, they took the opportunity to confront with gender topics in their university programs. It should be mentioned that this course started for the first time this Academic Year, 2015-16, at the undergraduate level. Several students showed their interest during the semester, when the course was already started, so we hope that next year the students’ participation will increase. However, it should be also mentioned that students have less and less freedom in choosing optional courses, therefore a further effort should be made in negotiating with the faculty a mandatory course focused on gender and equal opportunities.

Generally speaking, all the participants were really motivated to attend the Laboratory and to experience an applied research process. All the students expressed the necessity

to include more practical activities in the courses offered by the Department of Sociology and Social Research.

1.3.3 Noted challenges and evaluation

The five female students who took part to the methodological seminar were particularly motivated and interested in rising their knowledge about gender issues in contemporary sociological debate and understand how to include gender perspectives in research methodology. More precisely, they were particularly interested in experiencing research activities adopting a gender-sensitive approach.

The Laboratory was strongly interactive. We constantly invited students to be active, dynamic during the lessons, articulating their ideas and opinions, and presenting their work on the interview guide, on the questionnaire and, then, also on the interviews they conducted. Given the small number of participants, the atmosphere during the lessons was particularly relaxed and all the students actively developed all the proposed activities.

Generally speaking, the students do not openly resist to experience gender sensitive approach in their studies and research activities. The main difficulties they faced was to reflect about their gender positioning at university and more in general in the society, to understand how to separate their personal experiences by the case study developed during the laboratory, and how to include in their reasoning both the research evidences and the theoretical dimensions presented during the lessons in the first part of the laboratory, as well as considering the experiences gathered during the roundtable. We constantly asked to the students the effort to imagine the wider fan of experiences and situations they can envisage.

During the laboratory activities, students realised the difficulties to manage (their) stereotypes and prejudices about social phenomena, social and individual behaviours, attitudes, values, and preferences, and how (their) assumptions and expectations on gender roles can influence (and limit) both (their) research activities and (their) everyday life.

Sometimes, they explicitly expressed their frustration in maintaining a constant critical attitude on gender features and in managing the ambiguity and contradictions often hidden in social phenomena. This because they perceived them as a never ending story, like paradoxes without a solution. At the same time, they seemed to be really fascinated by the (gender) complexity inherent in social dynamics.

1.4 Actions implemented at the university level

In addition to the two actions described above, foreseen by the GARCIA Gender Action Plan in the STEM and SSH Departments, three further actions have been implemented at the University of Trento.

On considering the results of the organisational diagnosis and the workshops held with management and academic staff – in which the best strategies to implement the self-tailored GAP at the University of Trento were discussed – the GARCIA team was able to

undertake significant additional activities. These actions were planned with the aim of inducing the entire university and the citizenry of the province of Trento to reflect on the importance of integrating gender into research and teaching, and of stimulating young female students to pursue scientific careers.

According to these objectives, all the research centres and the departments of the University of Trento were considered. Also the local population was involved in the dissemination and training activities.

In order to attract as large an audience as possible, different languages were used, from storytelling to the cinema. There follows a description of the actions implemented.

1.4.1 Integrating gender into the “Researchers’ Night 2015”

In Autumn 2015, The GARCIA project collaborated with the FESTA project – and in particular with colleagues at the FBK – by including an event (the only one among the proposed activities) focused on female researchers in the “Researchers’ Night 2015”.

The Researchers' Night was held on Friday 25 September 2015 simultaneously across Europe. The purpose of the initiative, promoted by the European Commission in the continent’s main research centres, was to bring citizens closer to the world of research and to sensitize young people to scientific careers. Demos, workshops, research coffees and aperitifs, debates and flash talks presented the everyday routine of research and the work of researchers to a public of all ages.

In Trento, the event was held in the pavilions of Trento Fiere and at Palazzo delle Albere. It was promoted by the Bruno Kessler Foundation, the University of Trento, the Edmund Mach Foundation, and the MUSE Science Museum.

The GARCIA Project team organized jointly with the FESTA Project team the event entitled "FEMALE SCIENTISTS FOR A NIGHT! THE WOMEN RESEARCHERS’ NIGHT! Stories

of women scientists of the past, present and ... the future! ".

The event was addressed to all citizens and particularly to younger people. The public was guided in discovery of the scientific world and the contribution of women – often forgotten – to the development of scientific and social knowledge over the centuries. An interactive itinerary and animated readings narrated the biographies of important female scientists, their scientific results, and the usefulness of their discoveries for society. The initiative's motto was "Play to discover the scientist concealed within all of us." Visitors to the stand were given a deck of cards reporting the scientific discoveries of well-known female scholars, from Marie Curie to Rosalind Franklin or Margaret Mead, until more recent times with Rita Levi Montalcini and Margherita Hack. The public had to guess who had conducted the research described. On turning the card over, they could read not only the name but also a brief biography of the female scientist in question. Moreover, a corner of the pavilion was devoted to the reading of texts aloud by a young actress who collaborated in the initiative.

Set up in the tent for the card game and the theatrical readings were stalls providing information materials relating to the GARCIA and FESTA projects. As regards the GARCIA project, the stall distributed its brochures and information sheets on the actions implemented. Moreover, throughout the initiative, affixed to the walls of the stand were posters depicting the project's main areas of intervention and its actions. There follows a collage of the posters created specifically for the initiative.

Between 17:30 and 23:00, numerous adults and groups of boys and girls stopped to playing with the cards of women scientists and to listen to the readings.

Thanks to the initiative's success, it was selected from among the many ongoing activities to be presented on "Sanbaradio", the student radio station at the University of Trento, whose live broadcast on the Researchers' Night included an in-depth report on "Gender discrimination in academia". Below is a Facebook screenshot of the interview with Annalisa Murgia, the Scientific Coordinator of the GARCIA Project.

1.4.2 Integrating gender perspectives in the STEM and SSH fields

A second, university-level, action was developed jointly with the Centro Studi Interdisciplinari di Genere (Interdisciplinary Centre for Gender Studies). It consisted of a cycle of interdepartmental seminars for students on bachelor and master degree courses at the University of Trento, and members of the Centro Studi Interdisciplinari di Genere.

Involved in this initiative were various lecturers engaged in the GARCIA Project – Barbara Poggio, Paola Villa, Annalisa Murgia, Alessia Donà, Antonella De Angeli and Attila Bruni. In particular, thanks to the GARCIA Project and the involvement of Prof. De Angeli of the

Department of Information Engineering and Computer Science, for the first time a department relating to STEM disciplines was included in the series of seminars. This contributed to dissemination of the initiative in the science and technology departments and the participation of students also from the STEM disciplinary sectors.

167 people (153 women and 14 men) enrolled for the cycle of seminars, which was entitled GENDER STUDIES: INTERDISCIPLINARY PERSPECTIVES. Admitted to the course was a total of 80 people (71 women and 9 men) from: Faculty of Law (16), Departments of Humanities (16), Psychology and Cognitive Sciences (10), Economics and Management (7) International Studies (5), Physics (1) Mathematics (1), Engineering and Computer Science (1) and industrial Engineering (1). The rest of the class consisted of students enrolled at the Department of Sociology and Social Research.

There follows the course programme with the lecturers:

2 March 2016, 18:00 – 20:00

Genere e università [Gender and university]

Barbara Poggio, Dipartimento di Sociologia e Ricerca Sociale,
Università di Trento

3 March 2016, 18:00 – 20:00

Genere e educazione [Gender and education]

Giulia Selmi, Dipartimento di Scienze Umane, Università di Verona

9 March 2016, 18:00 – 20:00

Riflessioni sul genere [Reflections on gender]

Carla Locatelli, Dipartimento di Psicologia e Scienze Cognitive,
Università di Trento

10 March 2016, 18:00 – 20:00

Genere e Diritto [Gender and Law]

Luisa Antonioli, Scuola di Studi Internazionali e Facoltà di
Giurisprudenza, Univ. Trento

16 March 2016, 18:00 – 20:00

Caratteristiche e profili imprenditoriali delle aziende a conduzione
femminile [Entrepreneurial characteristics and profiles of women-
run businesses]

Mariangela Franch, Dipartimento di Economia e Management,
Università di Trento

17 March 2016, 18:00 – 20:00

Le differenze di genere: cause, effetti e politiche [Gender
differences: causes, effects and policies]

Paola Villa, Dipartimento di Economia e Management, Università
di Trento

23 March 2016, 18:00 – 20:00

Leggere le differenze di genere nel lavoro e nelle organizzazioni
[Reading gender differences in work and organisations]
Annalisa Murgia, Dipartimento di Sociologia e Ricerca Sociale,
Università di Trento

31 March 2016, 18:00 – 20:00
Genere e diritti umani [Gender and human rights]
Alessia Donà, Dipartimento di Sociologia e Ricerca Sociale,
Università di Trento

6 April 2016, 18:00 – 20:00
Il contributo della psicologia sociale alle differenze di genere [The
contribution of social psychology to gender differences]
Maria Paola Paladino, Dipartimento di Psicologia e Scienze
Cognitive, Università di Trento

7 April 2016, 18:00 – 20:00
Stereotipi e conoscenze in interaction design [Stereotypes and
knowledge in interaction design]
Antonella De Angeli, Dep. Information Engineering and Computer
Science, Univ. Trento

13 April 2016, 18:00 – 20:00
Fare scienza, fare genere [Doing science, doing gender]
Attila Bruni, Dipartimento di Sociologia e Ricerca Sociale,
Università di Trento

14 April 2016, 18:00 – 20:00
Principali concetti e metodologie della ricerca filosofica femminista
[Main concepts and methodologies of feminist philosophical
inquiry]
Giovanna Covi, Dipartimento di Lettere e Filosofia, Università di
Trento

20 April 2016, 18:00 – 20:00
Un altro sguardo sui classici: studi di genere e tradizione letteraria
[Another look at the classics: gender studies and literary tradition]
Francesca Di Blasio, Dipartimento di Lettere e Filosofia, Università
di Trento

21 April 2016, 18:00 – 20:00
Donne, femminilità e femminismi anni '70-'90 attraverso le riviste
[1970s-1990s women, femaleness and feminisms through
magazines]
Maria Coppola, Dipartimento di Psicologia e Scienze Cognitive,
Università di Trento

The cycle of seminars set itself the objective of introducing gender studies from an inter/multidisciplinary perspective. The gender perspective, in fact, enables interpretation of phenomena and processes, highlighting that gender differences and inequalities are major factors for full understanding of social, cultural, economic, political, and other contexts.

Students who participated for at least 22 hours (75% of the 28 hours of lessons, organised in 14 seminars) and wrote a paper on a topic covered in the cycle of seminars were awarded 4 university credits.

1.4.3 Film festival on gender and science

In the second semester of the academic year 2015-2016 the GARCIA Project began fruitful collaboration with the film festival on work organized for several years by the master course in Management of Organizations and Territory.

The 2015-2016 edition – in collaboration with the GARCIA project, the Autonomous Province of Trento and the Levi-Montalcini Association – devoted most of the films selected to gender differences in science and research, with specific regard to gender and sexuality.

For years, the film festival has explored the ways in which the cinema has represented stories, places and domains related to work, opening an arena for discussion for students not only of the Department of Sociology and Social Research but the entire University of Trento.

The films proposed for the 2016 edition centred on the theme of scientific work through detailed biographies of prominent scientists who, besides contributing significantly to their disciplines, have unquestionably revolutionized the society of their time. The films were shown in reverse chronological order, and therefore started from the present day and went back to the early 1900s.

The screenings began with *Elogio dell'Imperfezione. Incontro con Rita Levi-Montalcini*, an out-of-distribution documentary furnished by the Levi-Montalcini Association. The festival therefore opened with a tribute to the Nobel prize-winner for medicine, recently passed away, whom the festival wanted to commemorate also for her commitment to freedom and the rebirth of democracy in Italy. The series of meetings continued with the documentary *Hannah Arendt*, which reconstructed the period of the Jewish philosopher in the early 1960s, during the well-known Eichmann trial, which inspired Arendt's enlightening reflections on the 'banality of evil'. The third screening went back to 1948, the date of publication of the first work by Alfred Kinsey on the sexual behaviour of men and women, a milestone of social research on sexuality. The fourth projection returned to the European continent with *The Imitation Game*, a film on the life of Alan Turing, the man who broke the famous Enigma code used by the Nazi armed forces, but who ended his life in oblivion following prosecution as a homosexual a few years after the end of the War. The penultimate film of the festival recounted the achievement of the group of Italian physicists – *I Ragazzi di via Panisperna* – that formed around the figure of Enrico Fermi, the protagonist in the 1930s of revolutionary discoveries on the properties of slow neutrons which contributed to the future creation

of the atomic bomb. The cycle of meetings closed with *Madame Curie*, which recounted the early career of Marie Sklodowska Curie, a Nobel prize-winner in both physics (1903) and chemistry (1911) and still a symbol of excellence for all those working in the world of science and research. Illustrated below is the poster of the film festival:

The event was advertised by sending out emails and affixing posters in all the departments, both STEM and SSH, at the University of Trento. Moreover, an article was published in UNITRENTomag, the magazine of the University, available at: <http://webmagazine.unitn.it/vita-universitaria/8509/research-and-revolution>

The theme of the initiative was particularly appreciated within the University. This is confirmed by the fact that the staff of the secretariat of the Department of Sociology and Social Research and the University Library independently contacted the GARCIA team to collaborate with the film festival. In particular, compiled on the subject of the festival was a bibliography proposing a series of texts on science/scientists in the cinema and on the subjects of the individual films. Moreover, a bookcase in the library displayed a selection of books during the period of the festival. The bibliography is available at: <http://webmagazine.unitn.it/evento/sociologia/8097/research-revolution>

Around 100 persons per evening participated in the cycle of films. Projections were open to Trento University students, and to research, academic and administrative staff.

Moreover, for interested students of the University of Trento, the writing of a paper on the cycle of films granted 1 credit among those selected by the student. 42 students (27 women and 15 men) decided to opt for this possibility: 37 from the degree programmes

of the Department of Sociology, 3 from the Department of Industrial Engineering, and 2 from the Department of Humanities. The remaining public – about half – from all university departments attended the festival without asking for the recognition of credits.

Appendix 1 – Evaluation form of the training course implemented at the DISI

GENDER TRAINING - Workshop in Trento on 10/03/2016

Exit questionnaire

Name:

Your opinion matters. Thank you for giving us your feedback using the table below.

	Absolutely / very much	Quite	Rather not	Not at all
A) Did you learn what you expected to learn in this course?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
B) How satisfied are you with the following aspects of the training:				
• Relevance for your work	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Relevance for your own professional career	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Contents of the training	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Length of the training	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
C) How satisfied are you with the trainers:				
• Knowledge of the subject	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Communication skills	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Relation with the group	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Support and advice offered to participants	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Knowledge about participants' job	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
D) How satisfied are you with:				
• The visual supports	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• The documentation	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• The balance between theory and practice	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• The balance between individual and group sessions	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
E) Point out to what extent the training reached its objectives:				
1. Give an overview of the unequal position of men and women in research in Europe	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
2. Sensitize on the importance of a more equal participation of men and women in research	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
3. Indicate ways of stimulating a more equal participation of men and women in research	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
4. Inform about the concepts of gender and	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

	Absolutely / very much	Quite	Rather not	Not at all
gender mainstreaming and their relevance for research				
5. Sensitize on the importance of including the gender dimension into research projects and designing more gender sensitive projects	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
6. Indicate practical strategies to assist project applicants and teams with gender issues in their research projects	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
F) Overall, how satisfied are you with this training?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

PLEASE WRITE IN CAPITAL LETTERS

What did you expect to learn in this training session?

What are the main/most interesting points that you learned in this training?

What did you not find convincing in the training? Why?

To what extent do you find suggestions for gender-sensitive approach applicable to your work?

Did this workshop change your perspective on the presented gender-sensitive approach? If yes, how?

Do you think that you will be able to apply the contents of the training in your daily work or in your next research projects?

What could prevent you from using the acquired knowledge in your work?

If relevant, what are the issues addressed in the training you still feel less confident about?

On which topics addressed in the training would you like to know more?

Which topics that were not covered in the course would you suggest to address in future gender trainings?

Please feel free to add comments or suggestions:

Appendix 2a – The interview guide

UNA RICERCA IN OTTICA DI GENERE SULLE SCELTE UNIVERSITARIE E LE PROSPETTIVE OCCUPAZIONALI

Obiettivo: L'indagine si propone di studiare il vissuto soggettivo di studenti e studentesse universitari/e, con particolare attenzione alla costruzione delle differenze di genere. Si intervisteranno studenti/esse che frequentano laurea magistrali nell'ambito di discipline sia STEM che SSH. Si utilizzeranno interviste semi-strutturate, da realizzare seguendo la traccia qui presentata. Si focalizzerà inizialmente l'attenzione sui diversi aspetti dell'esperienza presente dello/a studente. Si analizzeranno poi i percorsi e le motivazioni che hanno portato, in passato, alla attuale condizione di studente universitario/a. Sarà infine esplorato l'immaginario futuro, relativo alla conclusione dell'esperienza di formazione, alle idee e ai progetti sulla futura occupazione.

1. Il vissuto attuale

- Potresti raccontarmi qualcosa del corso di laurea magistrale che stai frequentando?
- In questo momento abiti a Trento o fai il/la pendolare?
 - Con chi abiti? (indagare sesso coinquilini/e e corso di laurea/attività)
- Com'è organizzata una tua una giornata tipo?
 - quanto tempo dedichi alla frequenza delle lezioni e allo studio?
 - in questo momento stai anche lavorando? che cosa ti ha spinto a cercare un lavoro?
 - come occupi il tuo tempo libero? hai qualche hobby/passione in particolare (sport, volontariato, politica, ecc.)
- Pensando alla tua esperienza in questo corso di laurea, come ti sembra il rapporto tra compagni di corso?
 - vi frequentate anche al di fuori delle lezioni?
 - solitamente si tratta di gruppi misti di ragazze e ragazzi? hai mai percepito delle differenze tra ragazzi e ragazze del tuo corso? potresti farmi qualche esempio?
- Come ti sembra invece il rapporto con i/le docenti?
 - formale/informale
 - ti sembra che ci siano delle differenze tra ragazzi e ragazze? (indagare andamento scolastico / trattamento da parte di docenti, ecc.)
- Hai mai affrontato la tematica delle differenze di genere nelle lezioni che hai seguito durante il tuo corso di laurea?
- Durante il corso di laurea hai svolto qualche stage/tirocinio?
 - com'è stata la tua esperienza?
 - ti sembra sia stata utile per il tuo futuro percorso lavorativo?
 - hai percepito delle differenze di genere nell'azienda in cui hai fatto lo stage? se sì, potresti farmi degli esempi?

2. Il percorso progressivo

Scuola superiore

- Ti chiederei ora di fare un passo indietro nel tempo e di raccontarmi il tuo percorso di studi, a partire dalle scuole superiori?
- Che cosa ti ha spinto a scegliere quel tipo di scuola?
- Che suggerimenti hai avuto? (indagare parenti/conoscenti/insegnanti/amici)
- Pensi che la tua scelta di studi sarebbe stata diversa se fossi stato/a una ragazza/un ragazzo? pensi che i suggerimenti ricevuti da chi ti stava intorno sarebbero stati differenti?

Corso di laurea triennale

- Pensando invece alla scelta di studi universitari, che cosa ti ha spinto ad iscriverti a questo corso di laurea?
 - pensavi già a degli sbocchi professionali quando ti sei iscritto/a?
 - hai scelto la materia in cui andavi meglio o hai seguito altre motivazioni?
 - conoscevi qualcuno che prima di te aveva frequentato questo corso?
 - la distanza da dove abiti ha influito?
- 2. Come ti sei informato/a prima di iscriverti?
- 2.4 Che suggerimenti hai avuto? (indagare parenti/conoscenti/insegnanti/amici)
- 2.5 Hai partecipato a delle attività di orientamento? Avevi preso in considerazione anche altri corsi?
 - Pensi che la tua scelta di studi sarebbe stata diversa se fossi stato/a una ragazza/un ragazzo? pensi che i suggerimenti ricevuti da chi ti stava intorno sarebbero stati differenti?
 - Sei soddisfatto/a della tua scelta? ha corrisposto alle tue aspettative?

3. Il lavoro futuro: progetto e immaginazione

- Che cosa ti aspetti per il tuo futuro lavorativo? (indagare coerenza con percorsi di studi/di lavoro)
- Che strategie hai intenzione di mettere in atto in seguito al termine della magistrale per inserirti nel mercato del lavoro?
- Entro quanto ti aspetti di trovare lavoro? (indagare coerenza con titolo di studi)
- Hai preso in considerazione l'eventualità di trasferirti? in che contesto?
- Come immagini la tua vita privata?
- Pensi che essere un ragazzo/una ragazza potrà influenzare il tuo futuro lavoro? se sì, in che modo? e la tua vita privata?
- Finora abbiamo parlato delle tue aspettative, ma se non avessi alcun vincolo e potessi scegliere ciò che desideri, come vorresti che fosse il tuo futuro lavorativo? e la tua vita privata?

C'è qualcosa che non ti ho chiesto che pensi sia importante aggiungere rispetto al tuo percorso di studi e al tuo futuro lavorativo?
Posso chiederti alcune ultime informazioni?

Età:

Composizione famiglia

Titolo di studio e lavoro dei genitori

Titolo di studio e lavoro di fratelli/sorelle

Appendix 2b – Questionnaires

Schema of the questionnaire (lesson 10)

Target

- Studenti/esse prossimi alla laurea
- **Obiettivo. Confrontare percorso scolastico, lavorativo e aspettative per il futuro.**

Proposta di struttura del questionario

1. La situazione attuale

- Tipo di corso frequentato
- Quanto manca alla fine
- Quando si è iscritto alla magistrale?
- Quando si è iscritto all'università?
- Tesi? Relatore?
- Ha cambiato corso di studi?
- Motivo per cui frequenta quel corso di studi
- Mobilità geografica durante l'università
- Corsi di formazione/stage

2. Il percorso scolastico

- Tipo di scuola superiore frequentato
- Interruzioni, bocciature
- Voto alla maturità
- Anno diploma

3. Esperienze di lavoro pregresse

- Ha svolto un'attività lavorativa durante il percorso universitario?
- Con quale regolarità? Quanti lavori a svolto?
- Anno/mese di inizio primo lavoro
- Descrizione del tipo di lavoro
- Descrizione delle mansioni
- Anno/mese di fine primo lavoro

4. Lavoro attuale

- Anno/mese di inizio del lavoro (se diverso dal primo)
- Tipo di contratto
- Descrizione del lavoro
- Descrizione delle mansioni
- Anno/mese di fine primo lavoro

5. Futuro

5.1 – Lavoro desiderato / condizioni di lavoro / tipo di ricerca

5.2 – formazione post-laurea

5.3 – mobilità

6. – Transizione alla vita adulta:

6.1.1 Uscita dal sistema scolastico

6.1.2 Uscita di casa

6.1.3 Primo lavoro

6.1.4 Prima convivenza

6.1.5 Primo figlio

7. Informazioni Socio-demografiche (per discussione in aula)

7.1 Sei: [1] Maschio [2] Femmina

7.2 In che anno sei nato? _____

7.3 Sei nato:

[1] In Italia [2] In un altro Paese (specifica in quale Stato): _____

7.4 Se non sei nato in Italia, a che età sei arrivato in Italia? _____ anni

7.5 Dove sono nati tuo padre e tua madre? Una risposta per ciascuna colonna.

	Padre	Madre
In Italia	[1]	[1]
All'estero	[2]	[2]

(specifica in quale stato) _____

7.6 Se non vive da solo, può indicarmi quali persone abitano con Lei abitualmente (indicare il numero di persone):

1. Coniuge.....
2. Partner/convivente.....
3. Figli.....n.
4. Figli del coniuge/partner.....n.
5. Madre..... n.
6. Padre..... n.
7. Coniuge/partner del padre/della madre.....
8. Fratelli.....n.
9. Sorelle.....n.
10. Figli del coniuge/partner del padre/della madre.....n.
11. Nonni.....n.
12. Zii.....n.
13. Suoceri e genitori del partner/convivente.....n.
14. Cognati o fratelli/sorelle del partner/convivente.....n.
15. Altri parenti dell'intervistato.....n.
16. Altri parenti del coniuge, partner, convivente.....n.
17. Amici.....n.
18. Altre persone.....n.

7.7 Qual è il titolo di studio dei tuoi genitori? Una risposta per ciascuna colonna.

	Padre	Madre
Nessun titolo/ scuola elementare	[1]	[1]
Licenza media	[2]	[2]
Qualifica professionale (2-3 anni)	[3]	[3]
Diploma di scuola media superiore	[4]	[4]
Diploma parauniversitario/Laurea o titolo superiore	[5]	[5]

7.8 Qual è attualmente la condizione occupazionale dei tuoi genitori?

Una risposta per ciascuna colonna.

	Padre	Madre
Occupato/a	[1]	[1]
Disoccupato/a o cassaintegrato/a	[3]	[3]
Pensionato/a	[4]	[4]
Casalingo/a	[5]	[5]
Invalido/a o altra condizione non professionale	[6]	[6]
Deceduto/a	[7]	[7]

7.9 Se sono occupati, puoi descrivere per esteso qual è la loro attività lavorativa?

Se attualmente in pensione, disoccupati o deceduti, fai riferimento all'ultima occupazione svolta.

Ad esempio: bidello/a, titolare di una lavanderia, caporeparto in una industria tessile, parrucchiere/a, commesso/a in un negozio, impiegato/a in una concessionaria di auto, ragioniere/a in una ditta privata, titolare di un bar, dirigente in un ente pubblico, avvocato titolare di uno studio, commercialista assunto presso uno studio, insegnante di scuola elementare...

Occupazione padre: _____

Occupazione madre: _____

7.10 E se sono occupati, in particolare, sono... una risposta per ciascuna colonna.

	Padre	Madre
Lavoratore dipendente , e cioè:		
Dirigente o appartenente alla carriera direttiva (manager, capo ufficio, magistrato, primario, ufficiale...)	[1]	[1]
Impiegato (insegnante, bancario, segretaria, programmatore, ragioniere, poliziotto, infermiere...)	[2]	[2]
Operaio (capo cantiere, manovale, bracciante, commessa, fattorino, muratore, colf...)	[3]	[3]
<i>Oppure:</i>		
Lavoratore in proprio , e cioè:		
Imprenditore (con più di 4 dipendenti)	[4]	[4]
Artigiano, fino a 3 dipendenti (orafo, meccanico autonomo, parrucchiere, idraulico autonomo...)	[5]	[5]
Libero professionista (avvocato, notaio, architetto autonomo...)	[6]	[6]
Commerciante, esercente	[7]	[7]
Coltivatore diretto (contadino autonomo)	[8]	[8]

Final questionnaire

QUESTIONARIO

1. Situazione attuale

1.1 Può indicarmi a quale corso di laurea è iscritto/a? (1 sola risposta)

- [1] Economia
- [2] Beni culturali
- [3] Lettere e filosofia
- [4] Giurisprudenza
- [5] Ingegneria
- [6] Lingue
- [7] Ambito scientifico- matematico
- [8] Ambito politico-sociologico

A - IL PERCORSO SCOLASTICO

1.2 In quale anno accademico ha iniziato i suoi studi universitari? []

1.3 Se il suo corso di laurea non è a ciclo unico (per esempio: Giurisprudenza), che corso ha frequentato in triennale?

- [1] Economia
- [2] Beni culturali
- [3] Lettere e filosofia
- [4] Giurisprudenza
- [5] Ingegneria
- [6] Lingue
- [7] Ambito scientifico- matematico
- [8] Ambito politico-sociologico
- [9] Agraria
- [10] Altro (specificare)

1.4 L'anno della sua immatricolazione al corso di laurea magistrale corrisponde con quello della sua laurea triennale?

[Si] [No]

Se no, quanto tempo è trascorso? (indicare il numero di anni) N[.....]

1.5 Per quanto riguarda la laurea magistrale, su N. [] esami, quanti gliene mancano? N. []

1.6a Nella scelta del corso di laurea magistrale, è stato/a consigliato/a da qualcuno/a?

[Si]

[No] (passi alla domanda 1.7)

1.6b È stato consigliato da:

- [1] genitori,
- [2] fratelli/sorelle,
- [3] insegnanti,
- [4] amici o conoscenti

1.6c Crede che questi consigli l'abbiano aiutata nella sua scelta? [Si] [No] [In parte]

1.7 Per frequentare i corsi è stato necessario trasferirsi altrove rispetto alla sua città d'origine?

[Si] [No]

1.8 Durante il suo percorso di studi, ha frequentato: corsi di formazioni [Si] [No] stage/tirocini [Si] [No]

2. Percorso scolastico pregresso

Adesso le chiediamo di fare un passo indietro e di parlarci del suo percorso scolastico superiore.

2.1 Quale diploma di scuola secondaria superiore (maturità) ha conseguito?

- [1] Liceo scientifico
- [2] Classico
- [3] Linguistico
- [4] Liceo socio-psico pedagogico
- [5] Liceo delle scienze sociali
- [6] Liceo artistico
- [7] Liceo coreutico

[8] Istituto tecnico commerciale

[9] Istituto professionale

[10] ALTRO: _____

2.2 Qual è stato il voto con cui si è diplomato/a?

Esprimere in centesimi [][]

In sessantesimi se ha conseguito il diploma prima del 2001 _____

2.3 Nel corso della scuola superiore ha interrotto gli studi? [Si] [No]

Se Si: per quanti anni? N. []

2.4 Nel corso della scuola superiore è stato/a bocciato/a? [Si] [No]

Se Si: quante volte? N. []

B - LE ESPERIENZE DI LAVORO

1.0 Può indicare se ha già avuto un'esperienza lavorativa (sia lavoretti/sia lavori continuativi)?

Si [] (domanda 3)

No [] (domanda 2)

3.0 A quale età ha avuto la prima esperienza di lavoro? _____

3.1 Sono elencati qui sotto una serie di "lavoretti", potrebbe indicare se è un'esperienza che ha mai vissuto o che sta ancora vivendo?

(Dai "lavoretti" vanno escluse le attività domestiche per cui si riceve un compenso dai genitori, mentre vanno considerate attività di aiuto nell'impresa di famiglia)

Esperienza/e conclusa nel passato

Sì No

	Esperienza passata		Esperienza attualmente in corso
	si	no	
Un "lavoretto" continuativo nel tempo per almeno un anno (es. cameriere nei fine settimana, baby sitter la sera)	(1)	(2)	(1)
Un'esperienza continuativa di lavoro durata circa due mesi (es. stagione alberghiera, lavori estivi)	(1)	(2)	(1)
"Lavoretti" occasionali di breve durata (volantinaggio, promoter, dare ripetizioni...)	(1)	(2)	(1)

3.2a Attualmente svolge un'attività lavorativa retribuita? Le segnalo che l'apprendistato e i contratti di Formazione e lavoro vanno considerati come lavoro, mentre, le prestazioni che danno luogo solo a rimborsi spese non vanno considerate.

- NO, non lavoro [] saltare la "situazione lavorativa attuale"

- SI, lavoro [] passare alla "situazione lavorativa attuale"

3.2b Quando ha iniziato l'attuale lavoro __anno: _____ -

SITUAZIONE LAVORATIVA ATTUALE

4.0 Qual è la sua professione? Le raccomando di non usare termini generici come funzionario, impiegato o operaio. Indicare il livello delle competenze richieste e il campo delle competenze. Specificare il livello di responsabilità/autonomia associato

allo svolgimento della mansione. In diversi casi è necessario indicare il luogo dove l'intervistato svolge la sua attività.

4.1 Adesso le farò alcune domande relative alle caratteristiche del suo lavoro. Lei attualmente svolge un:

- lavoro autonomo [1]
- lavoro a progetto (o di collaborazione coordinata e continuativa o assegno di ricerca) [2]
- lavoro di prestazione d'opera occasionale [3]
- o un lavoro alle dipendenze? [4]

4.2 Tra le seguenti voci quale descrive meglio la sua posizione?

- E' un imprenditore [01]
- un libero professionista [02]
- un lavoratore in proprio (ad es. commerciante, artigiano, coltivatore diretto, ecc.) [03]
- un coadiuvante nell'azienda di un familiare [04]
- è socio di una cooperativa [05]
- o un lavoratore autonomo senza specifica qualificazione (ad es. collaboratrice familiare, trasportatore, conducente, commerciante ambulante)? [06]
- Altro [07]

4.3 Il suo lavoro è occasionale, stagionale o continuativo?

- Occasionale o Stagionale [1]
- Continuativo [2]

4.4 Il suo lavoro è a termine (a tempo determinato) oppure non ha scadenza (a tempo indeterminato)?

- A termine (a tempo determinato ,inclusi i senza contratto) [1]
- Non ha scadenza [2]

4.5 Lei con quale tipo di contratto lavora?

- Con un contratto di inserimento lavorativo (compresa Formazione e lavoro) [01]
- Con un contratto di apprendistato [02]
- Con un contratto collettivo nazionale di lavoro [03]
- Lavora per una agenzia interinale [04]
- Con un contratto a progetto o di collaborazione coordinata e continuativa (o assegno di ricerca) [05]
- Con un contratto di prestazione d'opera occasionale [06]
- Con un altro tipo di contratto a termine [07]
- oppure lavora senza un contratto? [08]
- con un contratto verbale [09]
- con un contratto a tempo indeterminato [10]

4.6 Lei lavora a tempo pieno o con un orario ridotto part-time ?

- a tempo pieno [1]
- part-time [2]

4.7 Lei quanto è soddisfatto del suo lavoro

1 Molto 2 Abbastanza 3 Poco 4 Per niente 9 Non risponde

- 8.A rispetto alle mansioni che svolge?..... 1
- 8.B rispetto alla stabilità o alla sicurezza del posto di lavoro?..... 1
- 8.C quanto è soddisfatto rispetto al grado di autonomia sul lavoro, molto, abbastanza, poco o per niente?..... 1
- 8.D rispetto all'utilizzo delle conoscenze acquisite all'università? 1
- 8.E rispetto al trattamento economico, molto, abbastanza, poco o per niente?..... 1
- 8.F rispetto alla possibilità di carriera?..... 1

4.8 La preparazione scolastica ricevuta si è rivelata utile per lo svolgimento dell'attuale attività lavorativa? (1 sola risposta)

- Molto
- Abbastanza
- Poco
- Per niente
- Non so

FUTURO LAVORATIVO

5.0 Che tipo di lavoro ti piacerebbe svolgere nel corso della vita?

5.1 Se dovessi scegliere, preferiresti lavorare a tempo pieno o part-time?

- a tempo pieno [1]
- part-time [2]
- non ha preferenze [3]

5.3 Vorresti lavorare come dipendente o in modo autonomo?

- dipendente [1]
- autonomo [2]
- non ha preferenze [3]

5.4a Saresti disposto a lavorare:

- ovunque, sia in Italia che all'estero [1] saltare il quesito 5.4b
- oppure solo in Italia? [2] passare al quesito 5.4b

5.4b Per lavorare saresti disposto a cambiare città?

- NO 1
- SI 2

5.5 Qual è la cifra minima che saresti disposto ad accettare mensilmente al netto per un lavoro come quello che hai appena descritto?

guadagno mensile netto in EURO [][][][][]

5.6 Ogni persona desidera dal proprio lavoro cose differenti.

Per Lei, personalmente, quanto sono importanti i seguenti aspetti del lavoro? Lo esprima sulla scala da 1 a 10 (1= Per niente importante – 10 = Importantissimo) (1 risposta per ogni riga)

	Per niente importante 1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	Importantissimo 10
a) Retribuzione/Guadagno economico										
b) Tempo necessario per raggiungere il luogo di lavoro										
c) Utilizzo delle Sue capacità										
d) Interesse per quello che fa										
e) Prestigio sociale del lavoro svolto										
f) Stabilità del posto di lavoro										
g) Orari di lavoro										
h) Autonomia nell'organizzare il proprio lavoro										
i) Possibilità di fare carriera										
j) Possibilità di influenzare le decisioni										
k) Possibilità di crescita delle proprie capacità professionali										
l) Possibilità di esprimere la Sua creatività										
m) Utilità sociale del lavoro svolto										
n) Rapporti con i colleghi										
o) Rapporti con i superiori										

5.7 Per trovare lavoro oggi in Italia quali sono i due fattori più importanti?

(1 risposta per ogni colonna) 1° posto 2° posto

1. Avere l'aiuto di persone influenti
2. Essere competenti
3. Sapersi presentare bene
4. Avere fortuna
5. Essere tenaci nella ricerca del lavoro

6. Sapersi accontentare

5.8 Per fare carriera oggi in Italia, quali sono i due fattori più importanti?

(1 risposta per ogni colonna) 1° posto 2° posto

- 1) L'anzianità lavorativa
- 2) Competenza
- 3) Fortuna
- 4) La disponibilità a lavorare molto
- 5) Essere sempre aggiornati
- 6) Assecondare i superiori

5.9a Dopo la laurea intende fare esami di stato per l'abilitazione all'esercizio di un'attività professionale?

- SI..... [1]

- NO..... [2]

5.9b Se sì, per quale professione? _____

5.10 Dopo il conseguimento della laurea sarebbe interessato a frequentare:

a) un dottorato di ricerca: lo sta frequentando, lo ha già concluso, lo ha interrotto o non l'ha mai svolto?	Si [1]	No[2]
b) una specializzazione post-laurea (esclusi corsi di perfezionamento e master)	Si [1]	No[2]
c) un master extrauniversitario	Si [1]	No[2]
d) una borsa di studio o di lavoro?	Si [1]	No[2]
e) uno stage?	Si [1]	No[2]
f) uno tirocinio o il praticantato?	Si [1]	No[2]
g) un corso di formazione professionale o di aggiornamento (di durata superiore a sei mesi o a 600 ore)	Si [1]	No[2]
h) un'altra attività di studio e formazione (includere i corsi di formazione professionale/aggiornamento fino a sei mesi o a 600 ore)?	Si [1]	No[2]
i) ore)?	Si [1]	No[2]

5.11 Se ci fossero delle buone formazioni all'estero sarebbe disposto/a a spostarsi?

Si
No

TRANSIZIONE ALLA VITA ADULTA

6.0 Può indicare se prevede di iniziare un'attività lavorativa nei prossimi 5 anni? (1 sola risposta)

1. Sono sicuro che inizierò a lavorare continuativamente entro i prossimi 5 anni
2. Credo che inizierò a lavorare continuativamente entro i prossimi 5 anni
3. Non credo che inizierò a lavorare continuativamente entro i prossimi 5 anni
4. Non ho intenzione di iniziare un'attività lavorativa retribuita in futuro
5. Non so, non posso prevedere

6.1 Può indicare se è andato a vivere in modo definitivo fuori dalla famiglia di origine (escludendo i trasferimenti temporanei per motivi di studio/lavoro) oppure prevede che ciò possa accadere nei prossimi 5 anni? (1 sola risposta)

1. Sono già andato a vivere definitivamente fuori dalla famiglia di origine quando avevo _____ anni
2. Sono sicuro che andrò definitivamente a vivere fuori dalla famiglia di origine entro i prossimi 5 anni
3. Credo che andrò a vivere definitivamente fuori dalla famiglia di origine entro i prossimi 5 anni
4. Non credo che andrò a vivere definitivamente fuori dalla famiglia di origine entro i prossimi 5 anni
5. E' escluso che nei prossimi 5 anni andrò definitivamente a vivere fuori dalla famiglia di origine
6. Non so, non posso prevedere

6.2a Pensi che per te sarebbe possibile cambiare città in futuro?

[Si] [No]

6.2b Saresti disposto/a a spostarti all'estero?

[Si] [No]

6.3 Ti piacerebbe iniziare un'attività di volontariato?

[Si] specifica: _____
[No]

6.4 Ci può indicare se si è sposato o ha iniziato una convivenza stabile con un/una partner oppure se prevede che ciò possa accadere nei prossimi 5 anni? (1 sola risposta)

1. Mi sono già sposato/andato a convivere quando avevo _____ anni e questa unione continua tuttora
2. Mi sono già sposato/andato a convivere quando avevo _____ anni ma dopo _____ anni
3. l'unione si è sciolta
4. Sono sicuro che mi sposerò/andrò a convivere entro i prossimi 5 anni
5. Credo che mi sposerò/andrò a convivere entro i prossimi 5 anni
6. Non credo che mi sposerò/andrò a convivere entro i prossimi 5 anni
7. E' escluso che nei prossimi 5 anni mi sposerò/andrò a convivere
8. Non so, non posso prevedere

6.5 Se dovessi scegliere tra le seguenti possibilità di convivenza, quale le sembrerebbe più desiderabile per il suo futuro?

1. da solo.
2. con la famiglia di origine (genitore/i e/o fratelli, sorelle)
3. con amici
4. con il coniuge/convivente
5. con figli
6. con altri parenti o affini
7. Altro

6.6 PER COLORO CHE NON ABITANO CON LA FAMIGLIA D'ORIGINE

Quando ha lasciato la casa dei Suoi genitori Lei:

(1 risposta per ogni riga) Si No

- Aveva trovato un lavoro stabile
- Aveva un reddito sufficiente a mantenersi da solo/a
- Aveva una casa di proprietà
- Aveva trovato uno o più amici con cui andare ad abitare
- Aveva trovato una ragazza/un ragazzo con cui andare a convivere.....
- Si era già sposato/a.....
- Aveva avuto il consenso dei Suoi genitori
- Aveva avuto un aiuto economico dei genitori.....
- Aveva un sostegno economico dallo Stato/Provincia/Comune
- Aveva un aiuto per le faccende domestiche.....
- Aspettava un bambino/Avevo avuto un figlio
- Aveva dovuto trasferirsi per lavoro

6.7 PER CHI NON E' SPOSATO O NON CONVIVE CON UN PARTNER

Attualmente Lei ha un ragazzo/ragazza (anche se non convive)?

- Sì
 No

E da quanto tempo ha questo rapporto?

- Da meno di 1 anno Da 3-4 anni
 Da 1-2 anni Da 5 o più anni

6.8 PER CHI VIVE CON LA FAMIGLIA D'ORIGINE

Lei vive con i Suoi genitori: (1 sola risposta)

- Abitualmente
 Non in modo continuativo, vivo per alcuni periodi dell'anno, fuori dalla mia famiglia

6.9 Ci può indicare se ha avuto figli oppure se prevede che ciò possa accadere nei prossimi 5 anni?

(1 sola risposta)

- 1) Ho già avuto un figlio quando avevo _____ anni (specificare l'età che aveva quando è nato il 1° figlio)
- 2) Sono sicuro/a che avrò un figlio entro i prossimi 5 anni
- 3) Credo che avrò un figlio entro i prossimi 5 anni
- 4) Non credo che avrò un figlio entro i prossimi 5 anni
- 5) E' escluso che nei prossimi 5 anni avrò un figlio
- 6) Non so, non posso prevedere

6.10 Ci può indicare quanti figli pensa che avrà complessivamente? (1 sola risposta)

- 1) Penso che ne avrò n° _____
- 2) Non penso che avrò figli
- 3) Non so

4) Non ci ho mai pensato

Informazioni Socio-demografiche

Lei è: [1] Maschio [2] Femmina [3] Altro (specificare) _____

7.1 In che anno è nato? _____

7.2 E' nato:

[1] In Italia [2] In un altro Paese (specifica in quale Stato): _____

7.4 Se non è nato in Italia, a che età è arrivato in Italia? _____ anni

7.5 Vive da solo? [Si] [No] (-> se si vada alla domanda 7.8)

7.6 Con quante persone vive abitualmente (lei escluso)? _____

7.7 Vive con almeno uno dei suoi genitori? [1] Sì, entrambi [2] Sì, uno [3] No

7.8 Ha fratelli e sorelle? [1] Sì [2] No (se NO, vada alla domanda 7.9)

7.8b [1] Sorelle, n: _____ 2 Fratelli, n: _____

7.8c i suoi fratelli e sorelle sono (più risposte possibili):

[1] più vecchi di lei

[2] più giovani di lei

[3] coetanei/gemelli

7.9 I suoi genitori sono:

1.Sposati

2.Conviventi

3.Divorziati

4.Separati

5.Altro _____

7.10 Dettagli sui genitori.

	GENITORE 1	GENITORE 2
a) I suoi genitori Sono:	[1] Maschio [2] Femmina [3]altro (specificare)_____	[1] Maschio [2] Femmina [3]altro (specificare)_____
b) Anno di nascita	_____	_____
	[9]Non so	[9]Non so
c) Sono ancora in vita?	[1]Si [2] No	[1]Si [2] No
c) Sono/erano nati: In Italia	[1]	[1]
All'estero	[2]	[2]
(specifica in quale stato)	_____	_____
d) Titolo di studio:		
1. Nessun titolo/ scuola elementare	[1]	[1]
Licenza media	[2]	[2]
Qualifica professionale (2-3 anni)	[3]	[3]
Diploma di scuola media superiore	[4]	[4]
Diploma parauniversitario/Laurea o titolo superiore	[5]	[5]
e) Attuale condizione occupazionale :		
1) Occupato/a	[1]	[1]
2) Disoccupato/a	[2]	[2]
3) Pensionato/a	[3]	[3]
4) Inattivo/a (casalingo/a, studente/ssa etc...)	[4]	[4]
f) Se inattivo, ha mai svolto una attività lavorativa nella sua vita?	[1]Si [2] No	[1]Si [2] No
f) Può descrivere per esteso qual è la loro attività lavorativa? <i>Se attualmente in pensione, disoccupati o inattivi con almeno una esperienza lavorative, fare riferimento all'ultima occupazione svolta</i> <i>Ad esempio: bidello/a, titolare di una lavanderia, caporeparto in una industria tessile, parrucchiere/a, commesso/a in un negozio, impiegato/a in una concessionaria di auto, ragioniere/a in una ditta privata, titolare di un bar, dirigente in un ente pubblico, avvocato titolare di uno studio, commercialista assunto presso uno studio, insegnante di scuola elementare...</i>	_____ _____ _____ _____ _____ _____ _____ _____ _____	_____ _____ _____ _____ _____ _____ _____ _____ _____
Questo lavoro è/veniva svolto Lavoratore dipendente , e cioè:		
1) Dirigente o appartenente alla carriera direttiva (manager, capo ufficio, magistrato, primario, ufficiale ...)	[1]	[1]
2) Impiegato (insegnante, bancario, segretaria, programmatore, ragioniere, poliziotto, infermiere ...)	[2]	[2]
3) Operaio (capo cantiere, manovale, bracciante, commessa, fattorino, muratore, colf...)	[3]	[3]
<i>Oppure:</i> Lavoratore in proprio , e cioè:		
4) Imprenditore (con più di 4 dipendenti)	[4]	[4]
5) Artigiano, fino a 3 dipendenti	[5]	[5]
6) Libero professionista (avvocato, notaio, architetto autonomo ...)	[6]	[6]
7) Commerciante, esercente	[7]	[7]
8) Coltivatore diretto (contadino autonomo)	[8]	[8]

2. Belgium

By Grégoire Lits

2.1 Introduction

The objective of organising training courses on how to integrate gender perspective in research and teaching is twofold: 1/ to raise awareness on how gender could be relevant for different academic fields; and 2/ to develop strategies for integrating a gender perspective in research and teaching.

2.1.1 UCLouvain context: The 2020 Gender Action Plan

At UCLouvain, the question of gender inequalities in universities has recently been raised as a matter of concern for the institution. This led, in June 2015, the “academic board” of the university (one of the most important governance body of the institution), to approve an official “Gender Action Plan” for the whole university. In the same movement, the “Gender Action Plan” has been made one of the nine “strategic axis” (with other axis such as “research” or “administrative simplification”) that the new rector and his team (elected in 2014) set up for the development of UCLouvain in the next decade.

In order to achieve this objective, the rectoral board nominated an official “counsellor of the rector” for the gender policy who has three missions to fulfil: guiding the Gender Action Plan of UCLouvain for all categories of employee; coordinating all activities connected to the question of gender in research, teaching and service to society; and, bring more sexual diversity in the governance structure of the university.

The UCLouvain team of researchers involved in the GARCIA project works in close coordination with the appointee for gender policy. As organizing training sessions on how to integrate gender perspective in research and teaching clearly falls under her umbrella, we proposed her to co-host these training sessions as part of the activities she could support through the UCLouvain Gender Action Plan, which she agreed to.

2.1.2 Organisation of the training sessions

We organised one training session in every institute taking part in the GARCIA project: the Earth and Life Institute (ELI, STEM) and the Institute for the Analysis of Social Change (IACCHOS, SSH).

The first training session took place at IACCHOS on 25 May 2016. The second took place at ELI on 1 June 2016. The duration of the training was two hours. As this period in the year is a no course period, it was a good time to organise a training where professors or full professors could easily take part.

The invitations to the training session were sent to all the members (professors, researchers, PhD students on contract and administrative staff) of both institutes

directly by the two presidents of the Institute. In both institutes, more than 100 people were personally invited to take part in the training.

The training session was presented to potential participants as an “exchange” with the Professor Van Hemelryck, rector’s counsellor for the gender policy. It was thus presented as an official activity supported by the institutes and by the rector (through his counsellor). This training was also the first official activity organised by the rector’s gender counsellor at the Institute level, and the first official local presentation of the newly approved Gender Action Plan of the university.

The invitation e-mail presented the structure of the training composed of: 1/ a presentation of the Gender Action Plan by the rector’s counsellor, 2/ a presentation by prof. Bernard Fusulier of some of the conclusions of the research conducted under the GARCIA project and 3/ a time for exchange.

The first training session organised in IACCHOS was not a great success since only two members of the Institute (namely its president and its former president) attended it. The second training session in ELI gathered 10 participants (the president of the institute, 1 professor, 1 post-doc researcher and 7 administrative staff members). It is worth noting that in the ELI institute, several members of the administrative staff of the institute were sent to the training by a professor who was supportive of the activity but was not able to participate.

We have no explanation on why so few people attended the IACCHOS training. We know that the invitations arrived well and that the members of the institute were well aware of the training. As professor and full professors have heavy schedule to manage, it may explain the low participation rate of this category of potential participants.

2.2 Course materials

In both institutes the presentation followed the same structure.

In a first part the rector’s gender counsellor gives a 30-minute talk about the UCLouvain 2020 Gender Action Plan. The presentation covered six different topics:

- 1/ Presentation of some statistics regarding gender balance at UCLouvain.
- 2/ Presentation of the main goals of the UCLouvain Gender Action Plan
- 3/ Presentation of the “action perimeter” of the action plan.
- 4/ Presentation of the different work packages of the Gender Action Plan
- 5/ Presentation of the actions already performed
- 6/ Presentation of some achievements already made

The first half of the talk was devoted to show actual statistics. The departure point was the presentation of the classical “scissor curve” that describe the leaky pipeline phenomenon in research institution with actual numbers for UCLouvain (see Fig. 1)

FIG. 1. The leaky pipeline “scissor curve” in the UCLouvain context

This graph clearly shows that gender inequality is a reality at UCLouvain and that actions should be undertaken to reduce the gap between male and female in advanced stages of academic career.

Others interesting data were presented that address the question of gender inequality for different categories of university employees or in different faculties and institutes of the university (see e. g. Fig. 2 and Fig. 3)

Fig. 2. Percentage of women in different employee status at UCLouvain

Type de personnel	Femmes	Hommes	Pourcentage de F
Académiques	129	395	25 %
Permanent·e·s FNRS (dont 3 LICR)	40	80	33 %
Académiques à l'heure	30	74	29 %
Académiques cliniques	65	179	27 %
Directeur·rice·s et enseignant·e·s ex-ISA/LOCI	12	25	32 %
Scientifiques	883	1 032	46 %
Maîtres de langues	43	15	74 %
Personnel administratif et technique	979	691	59 %
Résultat global	2 180	2 490	47 %

Fig. 3. Percentage of women students in the different faculties of UCLouvain

After presenting these statistics, the rector's counsellor presented the three main goals of the UCLouvain Gender Action Plan:

- 1/ promoting equality for all, men and women, in every category that composes the university (students, administrative staff, temporary researchers, and faculty staff).
- 2/ promoting and encouraging actions that aim at fostering gender equality and equal opportunities.
- 3/ raising awareness among university members on the importance of gender diversity and mixed-sex education for the wellbeing of its students and staff members.

Finally, the rector's counsellor presented some achievements and realisations made at UCLouvain, such as the creation of a research network in gender studies (the GREG network), the creation of a minor study program in gender studies, or an advertisement campaign to convince more female students to undertake studies in male dominated field like engineering.

The second part of the presentation consisted of a 30-minute presentation, made by a senior researcher involved in the GARCIA project. The aims of this second presentation were: 1/ to give a general overview on what are gender studies and why gender is an important question to tackle in our society today and 2/ to link current changes in university governance and organisation to the question of gender inequality and the difficulties in achieving good work/life balance for university staff members.

2.3 Participants' feedback and noted challenges

As said below, attendance at the two trainings were quite different. In consequence, the dynamics of the two training were very different.

2.3.1 IACCHOS

The IACCHOS meeting was only attended by the president and the former president of the institute (we thus reached 2 IACCHOS members out of 241 members). The last part of the training, the exchange with the participants, took the form of an open discussion between these two professors and the two presenters.

It is worth noting that both participants are senior professor of sociology that have strong knowledge in the field of gender studies (one of them being a specialist in the field of sociology of family and the other in the field of social justice and sociology of work). In consequence, the discussion went mainly about how to improve the presentation done by the rector's gender advisor (who is not herself a researcher in gender studies) if she wants to talk with an audience that is not quite familiarised with the question of gender. Feedbacks were also given about how to improve the UCLouvain Gender Action Plan.

From the discussion, but also from evidence collected during other activities conducted under the GARCIA project, we could make the hypothesis that the low attendance rate to the IACCHOS training session could be explained by the fact that some social science researchers of IACCHOS consider themselves as already very aware of the question of gender. We have been able to observe that, more often, professor of this institute tend to consider their institute as better in terms of gender equality than other institute of the university (even if there is no concrete evidence that this is really the case). This conception was probably reinforced by the fact that IACCHOS host the UCLouvain network on gender studies, and is also one of the driving force of the study programme in gender studies. The fact that the student population in the social and political sciences is well balanced in term of gender ratio could also be an explanation of this lack of interest in gender training.

One challenge regarding training for the IACCHOS institute should be to raise awareness to the fact that gender inequality is also a problem that have to be addressed in the institute of social sciences and that it is not only a problem of STEM disciplines, or of the university as a whole.

2.3.2 ELI

The situation was quite different in ELI. The training was mainly attended by members of the administrative and technical staff. Among the participant, 6 were women and 4 were men (we thus reached 10 people out of 335 ELI members).

Most of the participants seemed very interested in the two presentations. Several questions asking for more precise information were posed. Most of the attendants seemed to be quite convinced that gender is an important issue for ELI. Only one reservation was made, by the president of ELI (a senior professor) that attended the training saying that: “maybe the ELI institute [level] is not the good point of intervention”, suggesting that university or research centre levels would be more suitable.

Most of the questions asked during the last part of the training were demanding for more precise and accurate data concerning the ELI institute. Several comments have also been made that confirmed or agreed with the presentation of the results obtained during the GARCIA project presented by Bernard Fusulier, in the second part of the meeting.

Finally, it is important to note that during the training at ELI it was very difficult to address the question: “how to integrate gender perspective in research or in teaching?”. Most of the question of the participants were linked to the issue of inclusion of women in the student population or in the different categories of university staff members. Linking the issue of gender with the content of the research projects that are being carried out seems to be very difficult in this STEM institute.

2.4 Evaluation

Organising a training about how to integrate gender into research and teaching was no easy task. Despite the fact that the UCLouvain is committed to an ambitious Gender Action Plan, mobilising people about gender is still difficult.

At UCLouvain the different categories of staff members are strongly encouraged to take professional training. Newly hired professors have to take pedagogical training. They can have training on how to be good thesis supervisor, or how to animate an online course, etc. Teaching assistants have to follow training sessions on how to animate a working group, and administrative staff also have dedicated training sessions that they have to attend. These professional trainings are managed by an autonomous internal body within the university called the *Louvain Learning LAB*. To our view, one of the better ways to organise trainings on the question of gender would be to integrate a gender perspective into these already existing training programmes. This could be a long term and ambitious objective for a Gender Action Plan for the university, but it was not currently in our reach.

We thus decided and achieved to collaborate with the rector's counsellor for gender in organizing the first presentation of the UCLouvain Gender Action Plan at the institute level. These two trainings sessions at ELI and IACCHOS could thus be seen as a first attempt to communicate about gender in the UCLouvain and, to this regard, could be seen as an achievement in itself despite the fact that one of these events didn't exactly succeed in gathering a significant number of participants.

A lot of input about how to efficiently communicate about gender has been gained through these two first experiences and we have good hope that this sort of training sessions (conducted by the rector's counsellor) at the level of the institute will disseminate in other institutes soon, making the question of gender more visible in the UCLouvain.

For the GARCIA project, it is also worth noting that this experience was a first joint action with the central administration of the UCLouvain. Through the preparation of these two training sessions we have fostered the confidence and the good relations between the team involved in the GARCIA project and the central administration of UCLouvain responsible for the management of the Gender Action Plan. It is also an important achievement we have made through these training sessions.

3. The NETHERLANDS

By Yvonne Benschop

3.1 Introduction

This report concerns the integration of a gender perspective into research and curricula in the Netherlands, particularly Radboud University.

The participating STEM institute at the Radboud University in the Netherlands is the Institute for Mathematics, Astrophysics and Particle Physics (IMAPP). The IMAPP is one of the six research institutes at the Science faculty (FNWI), and is divided into four departments: Mathematics, Astrophysics, Theoretical High Energy Physics, and Experimental High Energy Physics. The Science faculty is one of the seven faculties of Radboud University.

The participating SSH institute is the Institute for Management Research (IMR). The IMR is the multidisciplinary research institute of the Nijmegen School of Management (NSM). The NSM is one of the seven faculties of Radboud University. The IMR conducts top-level research on the governance of complex societal systems. The IMR is divided into five sections: Business Administration, Economics and Business Economics, Political Science, Public Administration, and Geography, Planning and Environment. Each section is divided into different departments.

The specific context of the two participating institutes did not allow a specialized training for staff members to integrate gender in research and curricula. In the IMAPP, it was not considered feasible by the researchers and the contact persons to integrate gender in Mathematics, Astrophysics and Particle Physics research. To our knowledge, no examples are available of such integration in the literature. If integration would be possible at all, it would require a scholar well versed in both gender studies and the disciplines at hand. In contrast, in the IMR, there is already a situation of the integration of gender both in research and in curricula, because of the presence of a number of staff members who specialize both in Gender studies and in one of the IMR disciplines (Business Administration, Political Sciences, Economics). Both institutes require a different approach than training to integrate a gender perspective. We therefore report here on the actions taken to further the integration of a gender perspective in research and curricula.

3.2 Existing practices

For the integration of a gender perspective in research and curricula we started from the report 4.1.2, mapping the gender perspective in existing research projects and curricula at the two test departments of the Radboud University. The conclusions of this report are the following:

Within the IMAPP, no reference to gender or Gender studies can be found in research or in curricula. However, in the future, gender might get incorporated in the IMAPP's research, as in Horizon 2020 gender is a cross-cutting issue and is mainstreamed in each of the different parts of the Work Programme. For IMAPP, engagement with gender will mainly concern the representation of women and men researchers in the research teams, and not so much the integration of gender in the research projects. The research areas of IMAPP, Mathematics, Astrophysics and Particle Physics, are not linked to gender research. Research that does look at gender in the fields of mathematics and physics is only concerned with the performance of women and men students, and/or the representation of women in the staff. As for the curricula of IMAPP, there are no courses with any reference to gender perspectives. There is no gender expertise among the staff of the IMAPP.

Within the IMR, the number of courses and research projects that have gender as the core theme or that have gender-related themes are quite substantial. 21% of the MSc courses have a gender-related theme integrated in their course. Also amongst research projects in the IMR, five of the twenty analysed project descriptions contain gender or gender-related themes (25%). These percentages can be considered exceptional for a management faculty. This integration of gender in the research and curricula of the IMR can be largely explained by the relatively large number of gender experts among staff members and the research group Gender and Power in Politics and Management (<http://www.ru.nl/nsm/imr/our-research/research-groups/gender-power/>).

So, the starting point for the GARCIA project is one STEM institute in which there is no attention for gender in research and curricula at all, and one SSH institute in which there is already ample attention for gender in research and curricula.

3.3 Actions of the GARCIA project

The issue of integrating gender in research and curricula was taken up in the different action plans that we developed for the respective institutes. Below, we present the actions that were proposed and discuss how these actions have been implemented in the two institutes at this point in time (June 2016).

3.3.1 Action Plan IMAPP

As indicated above, we see no possibilities to integrate gender in the content of the research projects in IMAPP because we see no logical linkages between gender and the topics in Mathematics, Astrophysics and Particle Physics. In addition, this would require advanced knowledge on both gender studies and the disciplines at hand. For gender in curricula, we do see some potential in IMAPP.

Several options have been included in the action plan:

- Include gender topics in the course 'portfolio professional orientation'. This is both at BSc and MSc level and concerns the professional preparation from student to physicist, mathematician or astronomer on the job. Ideas to include gender concern:
 - guest lectures from women professionals, working both in and outside of science to provide female role models to students;
 - in discussions on career aspirations, supervisors should be keen to recognize and question possible gender differences and stereotypical choices;
 - gender as a theme, specialized classes around gender and careers, with focus on gender and academic careers with the goal to retain female talent for academia;
- point students to specialized courses in gender studies, available at the Nijmegen School of Management (Faculty of Management Sciences) and Institute for Gender Studies (Faculty of Social Sciences);
- attention for gender at the staff day on teaching: pay attention to the way staff advices and selects the next generation of scientists.

One other issue with gender in curricula is the lack of women teachers. Women are important role models for students and can inspire women to pursue a career in science. As few women staff members are currently employed, they should be strategically allocated in courses that reach many students. Furthermore, we suggest to involve women postdocs in teaching. A VENI-grant from the Netherlands Organisation for Scientific Research can be extended from three to four years when postdocs have a 25% teaching load. The Faculty (FNWI) could pay for the teaching part of the contract.

These actions have been proposed by the GARCIA team after discussion with the director of the IMAPP and the director of the educational programme of IMAPP.

After a change in the leadership of IMAPP a new director took over. The action plan, including the actions identified to integrate a gender perspective in curricula, has been further clarified in a meeting of one of the GARCIA PI's with the new management team of IMAPP. The new management team agreed to implement the proposed actions. Several formal and informal conversations with the director of IMAPP have been initiated by the GARCIA team to keep the actions on the agenda and follow-up on the progress made. The actions regarding the integration of gender in curricula were not prioritized by the IMAPP. We proposed to integrate a gender perspective especially in the course that prepares students for their later professions. So far, no further action was taken in this respect, other actions on gender equality were deemed more pressing first, such as the training for members of recruitment and selection committees.

It should be noted that the participation of the Faculty of Science in several EU projects (STAGES, GARCIA and EGERA) also contributed to the attention for gender. This resulted in the initiation of a gender committee within the Faculty who developed a gender and diversity policy 2016-2018. This committee is staffed by faculty members. Gender experts from the GARCIA and EGERA projects are advisory members of the committee. This committee is currently an important driver of the actions to be taken in the Faculty. Several working groups are active to implement actions, in particular regarding the representation of women in the staff, a €50.000 premium for research after maternity leave, more women on selection committees, and training members of selection committees. Most energy goes to actions regarding the representation of women in the faculty, and not much emphasis goes to the integration of gender in curricula and research.

3.3.2 Action Plan IMR

The situation at the IMR features an active and successful research hotspot on Gender and Power in Politics and Management. Therewith the level of integration of a gender perspective in research in the IMR is optimal and there is no need for further integration of gender in the research.

The GARCIA project inspired further action on the integration of gender in curricula. In the action plan for IMR we noted the following:

Gender studies have been part of the educational programs of the Nijmegen School of Management from the start. This makes it easy to continue along this road and further strengthen the visibility of Gender studies. We propose to follow a dual strategy of highlighting Gender studies in specialized minors in the BSc and the MSc and in a free MSc on Gender studies. Moreover, we propose to look for opportunities to integrate Gender studies in NSM educational programs that so far have little explicit attention for Gender studies, but where the potential is there (for instance in Economics and Public Administration).

The continuation of the research hotspot and the cooperation with other Gender studies research hotspots at Radboud University make Nijmegen the unique place in the Netherlands students and staff interested in this interdisciplinary field.

Proposed measures

- Minor Gender studies BSc
- Minor Gender studies MSc
- MSc specialization Gender studies
- Integration gender topics in general courses Business Administration / Political Science
- Integration gender in other curricula of the NSM
- Continuation of the research hotspot and strengthen the cooperation with interdisciplinary Gender studies courses at the Radboud University

The action plan, including these measures for the integration of gender in research and curricula, proposed by the GARCIA team, have been discussed several times with the dean and the director of NSM. They have agreed to implement these measures. With the arrival of a new dean (Spring 2016), we discussed the action plan with him as well and he also agreed to the implementation of these actions in the Faculty.

With regard to the integration of gender in curricula, a programme for a 30 ECTS minor gender studies in the bachelor program has been proposed. The bachelor minor consists of the two existing elective courses in Gender studies, 'Gender in Organizations' and 'Politics, power and gender'. One additional course has to be developed and we decided to go with a Capita Selecta Gender and Power course, differentially offered by the staff involved in the research hotspot. To get a minor programme, students need to write their bachelor thesis in Gender studies as well. Student advisors have to know about this minor program so they can advise students who are interested.

The development of a one-year MSc specialization Gender and Diversity is the most ambitious action and also the one that is favoured by the new dean. An MSc specialization allows for a clear link between the research hotspot and the educational programmes of NSM. The societal relevance of this MSc specialization is undisputed and it is linked to the mission of the faculty: "Creating Knowledge for Society". We developed an initial curriculum for this MSc specialization and discussed this several times with the management team of both Business Administration and Political Science. Originally, we intended for two new courses to be developed for this program. In the conversations with Business Administration it soon became clear that this was not deemed possible. Hence, a reconfiguration of courses was made so a full specialization could be offered based on a new combination of existing courses. The research on the availability of gender in the MSc curricula conducted for GARCIA 4.1.2. proved very helpful to identify courses for this program. We proposed two MSc specializations in gender equality, diversity and inclusion; one for Business Administration and one for Political Science. Both follow the same program, with exception of the methods course and one other course that is more disciplinary oriented to Business Administration or Political Science respectively.

The proposed curriculum is:

1. Gender Theories and Equality Policies,
2. Gender and Diversity in Organizations,
3. Multiculturalism, diversity and space
4. Organizational change / Power in political theory
5. The Politics of Reform
6. Organizational Research methods / Advanced research methods
7. Elective
8. MSc thesis

Further discussions about the eligible student population, learning goals and recruitment of students are ongoing. The plan is to start the new specializations in 2017-2018. The preparations to realize this are currently underway.

Another opportunity to include gender issues in curricula has occurred when the hotspot members were asked to develop and provide a course for the Interdisciplinary Honours Program. This is Radboud University's program for excellent students who can enrol for additional disciplinary or interdisciplinary courses in a specialized program. The course Gender and Power in Politics and Management was taught collectively for the first time in the year 2015-2016.

As for the collaboration with other Gender studies hotspots at Radboud University, an interdisciplinary consultation meeting has been established. One of the PIs of the GARCIA team is chair of this meeting that sets out to further develop interdisciplinary collaboration in Gender studies in research and curricula at this university.

3.4 Challenges and preliminary evaluation

The key challenges we encounter in the implementation of the actions regarding the integration of gender in research and curricula have to do with slow change processes in academia, and the multi-level complexity of gender that leads to a multitude of different actions regarding gender that get prioritized over this particular action.

Because of the work intensification in academia, change processes that are not seen as the core of education and research take a long time to become implemented. When it comes to issues of gender, it takes time to convince people that there is a problem at all, build knowledge about gender practices in organizations, identify important actions to be taken to counter the practices, get agreement about those actions from multiple actors involved, and finally implement them. These processes tend to take a longer time than feasible within 3-year project contexts. Pushing for change processes to speed up does not work and may even work against progress toward gender equality. A change in leadership of institutes and faculties working toward gender equality is a challenge for gender projects. A lot of effort is put into building rapport and understanding of the leadership for gender issues, and in times of leadership change, this often needs to be build all over again.

We do not encounter much overt resistance against the integration of gender, neither in IMAPP, nor in IMR. In the Faculty of Science (FNWI), the discourse is that there is a clear problem with the representation of women in the Faculty that needs to be remedied. Even though people tell stories about powerful professors who do not agree that gender is a problem and oppose gender equality in the name of scientific quality, we have seldom encountered this strong resistance. We do find, however, that discursive action is not paralleled by material action. Actions that need to be taken by the actors themselves, without a counterpart of the GARCIA project team initiating the action are not prioritized and are not (yet) implemented. This is a well-known problem with gender mainstreaming and one we see repeated in this context. We miss a change agent who is part of the IMAPP and feels responsible for the implementation of GARCIA actions and for keeping gender on the agenda as part of their regular work, not as an extra task on top of everything else.

We found that the energy to work on gender issues shifted during the project from IMAPP to the level of the Faculty of Science, following the installation and active work of the faculty's gender committee. We decided to link up with that committee, which is most promising at this moment to get things done. GARCIA members are involved in the actions proposed by the committee and as advisory members for the gender committee. While we think this is a positive development, there is also a challenge when multiple actions and interventions are going on at the same time. The full complexity of gender as a cross-cutting theme through research, teaching and personnel management in academia is not always fully understood. It can be perceived as gender 'overkill'; too much attention for gender in too many different areas. It can also lead to cherry picking: some issues are seen as more important or easier to act upon or remedy than other issues.

In the IMR, the general discourse is that the Faculty is already doing a good job with regard to gender issues. The representation of women in the staff is not seen as a problem, the presence of a substantial number of gender experts united in the research

hotspot, and the integration of gender in curricula are perceived as indicators that the Faculty is doing well in this respect. As this Faculty is the home base of the GARCIA researchers, it is easier to get things done, as it partly concerns our own teaching and research. So, there is more activity from the change agents at IMR as part of their daily work. This is making it easier for other actors to lean back and let them do the work. Keeping others informed, involved and active constitutes a challenge for gender projects and gender experts.

Overall, when we evaluate the integration of gender in research and curricula, we have made more progress in IMR than in IMAPP, where we need to start from scratch. This is certainly not impossible, but it takes a longer time, as the necessary commitment needs to build up first, followed by the development of the expertise and the implementation in the curricula.

In IMR, the GARCIA project has contributed to the development of an MSc specialization in Gender studies in two of the disciplines: Business Administration and Political Science. While negotiations about the finesses of the program are ongoing, this opportunity for students to specialize and obtain a final degree in Gender studies is the optimal integration possible.

4. ICELAND

By Thomas Brorsen Smidt, Gyða Margrét Pétursdóttir & Þorgerður Einarsdóttir

4.1 Introduction

At the University of Iceland there is a considerable scepticism towards active measures in gender issues as revealed in almost all WPs of the GARCIA project. Taken this into account the Icelandic team decided to integrate the “training courses on integrating gender perspective into research and teaching” into already existing initiatives and activities. According to the University of Iceland Equal Rights Policy 213-2017, guidelines/practical examples for integration in teaching and research shall be developed by the Equal Opportunities Committee.¹ These guidelines have recently been completed in collaboration between the Equal Opportunities Committee and the Centre for Teaching and Learning at the University. The University has however not yet developed guidelines regarding how to integrate gender into research. With this as a point of departure the GARCIA team decided to invite the Equal Rights Committee and the Centre for Teaching and Learning (CTL) to join forces in a workshop in which the newly adopted teaching guidelines and the GARCIA toolbox on research would be presented and a first step of gender sensitizing training would be taken. As the CTL has workshops and courses on a regular basis it was decided that the workshop would be organised as one of these events and advertised by the CTL. By this the workshop was open to all interested and not only academics in STEM and SSH. The workshop was advertised for all staff and students on the internal mailing list of the University, and on the CTL’s website, and all participants had to register online. Participants for our training course on integrating gender into research and teaching were informed of the time and place for the course via email invitation to all departments, detailing the purpose of the training. The training took place at a conference room in the Icelandic National Library, about a 5-minute walk from campus. Free lunch was provided so as to entice as many adherents as possible. In total 13 participants showed up for the training course. Of these, 5 were A level, 1 was B level, 2 were C level, 2 were administrative staff, 2 were in management and 1 was a graduate student: 12 women and 1 man. Curiously, most participants were from STEM.

¹ http://english.hi.is/university/equal_rights_policy

4.2 Course materials

The course material consisted of two presentations: One by two representatives from the (CTL) and one by a member of the GARCIA team.

The purpose of the CTL is to provide instructors at the University of Iceland with professional assistance in development of teaching methods. In addition to general consulting and development work, an emphasis is placed on continuing education courses for teachers in the fields of information technology and pedagogy. The CTL manages teaching evaluations, scanning and processing of multiple-choice exams, as well as providing assistance and consultation regarding pedagogical and technical aspects of distance education.

CTL presented the previously mentioned guidelines,² which were developed by the center in collaboration with the Equal Opportunities Committee as per demand in the University of Iceland's Equal Rights Policy. The UI Equality Officer has emphasized the importance of presenting this list to as broad an audience as possible, including the new staff. As it stands, the list is also used as a tool in a university teaching graduate course, which was started a few years ago. The list is developed on the basis of pedagogical views and trend within teaching methodology in which we have seen a steady change from a teacher focused perspective to a student-focused perspective in teaching pedagogy. Special attention is paid to speaking directly to students and getting to know students on a personal level, combined with the realization that power dynamics between teacher and student are important to be aware of. The representative from the CTL emphasised that gender issues can be seen as a natural continuation of the pedagogical perspectives inherent in all their work. Hence, although their daily work did not include gender issues they were easily integrated.

The guidelines cover practical as well as pedagogical questions in relation to teachers' engagement with students and is divided into **14** chapters, each dealing with a particular aspect of teaching.

To mention a few examples, the first chapter deals with the curricula and reading material and serves to ensure that teachers have an equal distribution of female and male authors in their prospective reading lists and that the reading material takes gender and social justice issues into consideration when relevant. Other questions deal with the teaching space and ensuring that all students have equal access to teaching. Teaching methodology was also addressed. Here special focus was put on the challenges of blind students, choosing diverse subject matter for discussion and making sure teaching visuals mirrored the diversity of Icelandic society. Other important headlines included guidelines on how to hire for assistant teachers that might improve the

² <https://kennslumidstod.hi.is/wp-content/uploads/2016/04/Jafnretti-i-kennslu-Gatlisti.pdf>

students experience as well as how to tackle questions of pornography or instances of sexual violence among students.

The presentation by the GARCIA team member focused on integrating gender equality into research and began by presenting arguments as to the need for a gender equality toolkit³ in this regard. This was done by presenting data from D4.1.2. Firstly, it was shown that the vast majority of external funding at the UI go to STEM research and that of the very few research projects funded in SSH, only a very small handful treat the topic of gender equality and social justice. This was presented while referring back to the UI Equal Rights Policy in which the integration of gender into research is defined as an obligatory practice. It was argued that levels of external funding do not adequately reflect the Equal Rights standards of the UI.

Example. 2.1. Slide showing the distribution of external funding in SSH & STEM respectively

A member of our team presented the GARCIA toolbox in two parts. Firstly, the part of the toolkit concerning the research team was presented. It was argued to the attendance that a growing body of literature has clearly shown the scientific long-term advantages of integrating a gender perspective into the process of forming a research team and maintaining an atmosphere in which gender equality is not just taken for granted, but is valued as a continuous process of self-reflection among researchers.

³ Toolkit for Integrating Gender Sensitive Approach into Research and Teaching

Example 2.2. Slide showing part of the toolbox regarding gender equality on research teams.

Example 2.3. Slide showing an example of how gender has not been integrated where appropriate

Finally, the toolkit for integrating gender in research was presented. Examples from the specific departments was used to show that despite an Equal Rights Policy that demands gender equality being integrated into research when appropriate, this is far from the case when it comes to actual research output.

4.3 Existing practices

The GARCIA team decided against distributing forms for participants at the opening of the training. This decision was made after considering the possible negative effects such forms might have on our desired outcome, which ultimately is to ensure a better integration of gender equality into research and teaching. We found that the questions (Do you find yourself to be gender-sensitive in your research? Have you integrated gender in any of your research projects? Have ever used gender-sensitive methodology?) were not appropriate for distribution in a setting which was the first step of gender sensitising training of the academic staff. While these questions might have been appropriate in certain setting, for example in SSH only setting, we feared that they might stir up animosity in an inclusive setting where academics from all disciplines participated. We knew beforehand that by distributing the questions every academic in STEM would answer 'no' to every single question. At best, this might have been perceived unnecessary, and at worst as spitefulness. Therefore, we ultimately decided against it.

4.4 Noted challenges

We were surprised to find that there was little to no resistance towards adopting a gender-sensitive approach in research among our training participants. This, however, might be explained by the fact that the training course itself was not obligatory and so persons with little or no interest in changing the status quo were perhaps unlikely to show up in the first place. In general, participants were open-minded and in agreement with the need for gender equality guidelines in research in and teaching.

However, participants did raise concern about whether or whether not the guidelines were universally applicable in all academic contexts. One participant from the School of Health Sciences pointed out that the checklist would require the expertise of health experts in order to appropriate it in a health science context. Other participants were in agreement and added that guidelines made in an SSH context might be difficult to integrate into STEM, which further raises the issue of finding experts in STEM fields who have the gendered know-how to appropriate the list in their specific contexts.

In the context of integrating gender equality into research, participants suggested that the Equal Rights Policy does not translate into the codes of practice surrounding hiring practices at the university and in the process of allocating funding for research. It was suggested that a clear code of practice for what kind of research should receive funding would help incentivise researchers to integrate the gender perspective when appropriate. It was also suggested that in hiring practices, applicants with a history of integrating gender and social justice perspectives in their research should be prioritized.

4.5 Evaluation / Conclusion

We arranged the training at the Icelandic National Library. 13 participants mostly from STEM were present. Our training was divided into two sections: Gender equality in teaching and gender equality in research. The first part of the training was carried out by two representatives from CTL, who presented and explained in detail the guidelines that they have been advocating and attempt to using for their graduate diploma course in university level teaching. Secondly, our GARCIA team member argued for the importance of the integration of gender equality in research and provided examples of benefits of doing so and examples of how the UI research output does not reflect the ideals of its Equal Rights Policy. We decided against letting participants fill out forms with questions that we already knew the answer to in an effort not to create animosity towards the ideas we were there to present. On the other hand, we received valuable input from a positive group of participants who provided valuable insight into how the checklist might be adequately appropriated in a STEM context and how different codes of practices in funding processes and hiring might bring Icelandic research and teaching up to a level reflecting the contents of its policies.

5. SWITZERLAND

By Sabine Kradolfer and Nicky Le Feuvre

5.1 Introduction

5.1.1 Existing structures at the UNIL for integrating a gender perspective into research and teaching

Before reporting on the workshops, it seems necessary to present the existing structures used for disseminating information and organising (or supporting) teaching and research activities from a gender perspective at the UNIL. As already mentioned in report 4.1.2 “Mapping the gender dimension in existing research and teaching activities,” the SSP Faculty (*Faculté des sciences sociales et politiques* – Faculty for social and political sciences) – our SSH department – at the University of Lausanne (UNIL) hosts an Interfaculty Gender Studies Platform (*Plateforme en Etudes Genre*, whose acronym is PlaGe)¹ and a Gender Studies Research Centre (*Centre en Etudes Genre* - CEG).

The first official Gender Studies Centre, the *Laboratoire Interuniversitaire en Etudes Genre* (Interuniversity Laboratory in Gender Studies – LIEGE)² was set up following feminist mobilisations at the UNIL in the late 1990s. After the 4th Women’s World Conference in Beijing in 1995, the Commission for Women’s Issues of the Rectorate (*Commission féminine du Rectorat*) asked for the creation of an interfaculty department for teaching and research on gender issues. Thanks to the continued mobilisation of feminist researchers, lecturers and students, the pioneer LIEGE was created in 2001, and housed in the SSP Faculty, mostly with external funding obtained through the 1st Federal Gender Equality in Academia Programme. In 2000, the first chair in Gender Studies at the UNIL was created, also in the SSP Faculty. The LIEGE became a fully-fledged research centre (i.e. structurally integrated and fully financed by the UNIL) in 2008, after eight years of activities, and changed its name to CEG-LIEGE (Centre for Gender Studies – LIEGE) and then simply to CEG, in 2016. Over the years, it shifted from an activist network of approximately 450 members (including many feminists from outside academia) to a small-scale specialist research centre.³ Part of the networking activities of the CEG – LIEGE were transferred to the PlaGe, officially created in 2012, which “is an interdisciplinary network whose principal goal is to [...] foster collaboration among the individual members of the UNIL in research, organisation of scientific activities, diffusion and integration of Gender Studies into the different disciplines and faculties of University.”⁴ Today, this interdisciplinary Gender Studies network has more than 100 registered members (from students to full professors). They belong to the different faculties (or to the central services of the UNIL) and some of them are former collaborators of the UNIL.

Since they were set up in the late 1990s, the Gender Studies centres at the UNIL (CEG-LIEGE-PlaGe) have carried out an annual census of all Bachelor and Master courses that

¹ Which means “beach” in French!

² <https://www.unil.ch/ceg/fr/home/menuguid/reseau-liege.html> [retrieved 24 June 2016].

³ <https://www.unil.ch/ceg/fr/home.html> [retrieved 24 June 2016]. For more information on the LIEGE, see Fassa and Kradolfer, 2014.

⁴ Translation from the website: <http://www.unil.ch/plage/home.html> [retrieved 24 June 2016].

include a gender dimension. The results of this census are available through the PlaGe web site.⁵ In 2015-2016, there were 40 undergraduate courses and almost 30 MA courses, which (according to their teachers) included gender as a central or peripheral object of study. Although the census probably under-estimates the degree to which gender is included in the teaching programmes of the different Faculties (since it requires academic staff to respond to the questionnaire that is sent out by E-mail at the end of each academic year), this census provides a useful tool for students who want to concentrate on gender issues as part of their degree course. The undergraduate course structure at the UNIL makes it possible for students to take courses offered by another Faculty on an optional basis and thus to reinforce the gender content of their initial degree programme, even in Faculties where there are few courses directly on gender issues.

In addition to this “internal” source, students can also access information about courses and research activities with a gender perspective through the Swiss national Gender Campus Newsletter and mailing list. Published in three languages (English, French and German), the Gender Campus website gives access to comprehensive information about all the undergraduate courses, doctoral training programmes and research seminars that include a gender dimension, for the whole of Switzerland (and, sometimes, in neighbouring countries).⁶ The website also provides links to the home pages of research projects that include a gender dimension, again, for the whole of Switzerland. Finally, information is also provided about equal opportunity initiatives in different higher education institutions in Switzerland. The Gender Campus project is funded under the Federal Gender Equality in Academia Programme and employs two part-time webmasters / mistresses, who are responsible for updating the information, most of which is provided by Gender Studies Centres in the different Swiss Universities.

In the case of Lausanne, most of the information comes from the CEG Research Centre, in the SHS Faculty, or through the interfaculty PlaGe network. When we wrote the 4.1.2. report one year ago, the CEG had just 5 “full” members: 1 associate professor, 1 permanent senior lecturer, 3 postdoc researchers, 1 PhD student and 1 student assistant. Due to a reorganisation among the different labs belonging to the Institute of social science of the SSP Faculty at the end of 2015, the CEG was able to develop quickly as one assistant professor on tenure track (now tenured as full professor) joined the CEG with her team and one new associate professorship was created (the hiring procedure is now completed and the new professor will start work at the UNIL in September 2016). So the CEG now has: 1 full professor, 2 associate professors, 1 permanent senior lecturer, 4 postdoc researchers, 3 PhD students, 3 student assistants, and the coordinator of the PlaGe, who is also a full member of the CEG.⁷

Some members of the GARCIA team belong to the CEG: Farinaz Fassa is a full member and Nicky Le Feuvre and Sabine Kradolfer are associate members, and they are all full members of the PlaGe. As they are also involved in the activities of the National Centres of Competence in Research (NCCR) LIVES⁸ (Nicky Le Feuvre as former head of the Equality sector, Farinaz Fassa as current head of the Equality sector and Sabine Kradolfer as

⁵ <https://www.unil.ch/plage/home/menuguid/enseignement.html> [retrieved 24 June 2016].

⁶ <https://www.gendercampus.ch/fr> [retrieved 4 July 2016].

⁷ <https://www.unil.ch/ceg/home/menuint/membres.html> [retrieved 24 June 2016].

⁸ <https://www.lives-nccr.ch/en> [retrieved 24 June 2016].

Equality Officer), we decided to organise the workshops in collaboration with the NCCR and to open them widely to all Faculty members in SSH. We also collaborated in the actions and events organised by the PlaGe, which addressed the whole university.

5.1.2 GARCIA workshops and activities for integrating a gender perspective into research and teaching

We will report on two workshops co-organised in the frame of the NCCR LIVES and other activities aimed at supporting actions organised by other UNIL members to integrate a gender perspective into research and teaching.

The first NCCR LIVES workshop “*Intégrer le genre dans les dispositifs de recherche qualitatifs et quantitatifs* (Integrating gender into qualitative and quantitative research methods)”⁹ was organised on 2 November 2015, by the LIVES Equality Office¹⁰ under the auspices of the Doctoral Programme of the NCCR,¹¹ but all members of the NCCR – from professors to PhD assistants – received an invitation to attend this activity. It was a one-day training event (see Appendix 1), which attracted 8 participants.

The second NCCR LIVES workshop, “*Les analyses quantitatives à l'épreuve de la perspective genre* (Quantitative methods under a gender lens),” was a half-day workshop organised on 25 April 2016, by the Equality Office, and an invitation was again sent to all members of the NCCR LIVES and to the colleagues in the UNIL SHS Faculty (see Appendix 2). This workshop attracted 8 participants.

Both workshops were organised at the UNIL and were outsourced to external experts. Table 1 shows the composition of participants to both workshops by academic grade and sex.

Table 1. Participants in the workshops organised by the NCCR LIVES by academic grade and by sex

	Participants	PhD Students	Postdocs	Female	Male
Workshop 1	8	8	0	7	1
Workshop 2	8	3	5	7	1

The participants in these workshop were all from SSH disciplines, and mainly from sociology and psychology. In fact, the second workshop was specifically aimed at psychologists and social-psychologists. Half of them were members of the NCCR LIVES. If we take in account that 180 persons are members of the NCCR LIVES (not all working at

⁹ https://www.lives-nccr.ch/sites/default/files/pdf/page/prodoc_2_novembre_2015.pdf [retrieved 24 June 2016].

¹⁰ <https://www.lives-nccr.ch/en/page/equality-and-parenting-n73> [retrieved 24 June 2016].

¹¹ <https://www.lives-nccr.ch/en/page/doctoral-programme-n11> [retrieved 24 June 2016].

the UNIL) and that the Institute for Social Sciences also has more than 150 researchers, we reached between 200 and 300 persons for each workshop.

It was more difficult to organise activities within the Faculty for Biology and Medicine (FBM), in which the Section for Basic Sciences is our STEM department, as our GARCIA agenda was different than that of the people in the FBM Faculty who were supporting or in charge of actions to integrate gender in teaching and research. As we experienced strong resistance to the implementation of actions that we could bring from “outside” the Faculty, we decided to offer our support and expertise to the different groups of people already working on gender equality and gender studies within the two departments (basic and clinical sciences) of the STEM Faculty. To discuss opportunities for collaboration, we organised two meetings (26 May and 19 June 2015) with the persons in charge of the equality action plans from each of the two (STEM & SSH) GARCIA departments, persons of the STEM department belonging to the support group in charge of integrating gender in research and teaching (Dr Carole Clair Willi, a medical doctor and co-chair of the PlaGe), the Head and other members of the Equal Opportunities Office, and the Chair of the committee in charge of postdocs & tenure track professors (*Commission de la relève*). After these meetings we kept in regular contact with these different actors, and in particular:

- We were invited as experts to attend the monthly meetings of the *Commission Pro-Femmes* (Pro-Women’s Committee of the STEM Faculty). During these meetings several topics to support women’s careers were addressed and among those that are important for this report, we discussed the usefulness of organising “Equality lunches” to create a network among the women with permanent and non-permanent positions working in the Faculty. Some women who are alone in their department complain about their isolation and could benefit from such an event to create support with women in other departments. The members of the committee emphasised any action undertaken should not be presented as “too feminist” because women professors might be reluctant to attend such a meeting. We analysed several potential formats for these sessions during the meetings and we intend to organise a first “Equality lunch” in September where we could match the networking event among FBM women with a conference open to men and women on gender in health issues (the topic is still under discussion).
- We met Dr Carole Clair Willi on several occasions and we were informed about the work of the support group in charge of integrating gender in research and teaching in the STEM Faculty. This project, which started some years ago with the writing of a report by Catherine Fussinger (2011), is still ongoing. It is also one strategic axis of the Faculty’s Action Plan, but it remained somewhat forgotten and lacked the necessary resources. Since the new deanship started on 1 August 2015, the vice-dean in charge of equality (Prof. Décosterd) has been very supportive, and an officer (Aurélien Georges, trained in social sciences but working on diabetes and tobacco addiction) has been hired to work on this project. Nevertheless, so far no action has yet been implemented, but we are in discussion with Carole Clair Willi and we offered to support this project during the six last months of the GARCIA project. Therefore, we will report on the outcome of the on-going initiative in our final scientific report.

5.1.3 Other activities with participation of GARCIA members

Beside these two workshops, members of the Swiss GARCIA team attended and intervened in different activities organised by other institutions or services.

- *Fabrique de la recherche du Réseau Etudes Genre en Suisse* (Research Workshop by the Network Gender Studies Switzerland),¹² 25-26 September 2015. “The Network Gender Studies Switzerland has existed since 2004. It is a programme for interuniversity cooperation in which nine Swiss universities pool their teaching and research activities in Gender Studies. With financial backing from the Conference of Swiss Universities until the end of 2016, the Network has proved to be successful as a cooperation project aimed at institutionalising Gender Studies”.¹³ The aim of this national meeting was to prepare the sustainability of the network after 2016. Nicky Le Feuvre was invited to take part in the roundtable on “Perspectives for the future for the Network Gender Studies Switzerland” and Sabine Kradolfer took part in a workshop on “Gender Studies in Science, in Switzerland”.
- Farinaz Fassa presented a paper, “*Politiques d’égalité dans les universités. Du top-down au bottom-up, quels enjeux?* (Equality policies in universities. From top-down to bottom-up, what challenges?)”, during the *Journée de la recherche sur le genre* (Gender Studies Research Day)¹⁴ organised by the PlaGe (15 March 2016).
- Sabine Kradolfer attended the workshop on scientific publication organised at the UNIL on 14 April 2016 by junior researchers (Cécile Charlap, Stéphanie Pache and Laura Piccand) on the occasion of the publication of the special issue “*La construction scientifique des sexes* (The scientific construction of the sexes)” they edited for the journal *Émulations* (n°15, 2015). This workshop was followed by a lecture by Julie De Ganck entitled “*Cultiver la différence des sexes: la spécialisation de la gynécologie à Bruxelles* (Cultivating sex difference: the specialisation of gynaecology in Brussels)”.¹⁵
- On 14 June 2016, an important public event on the anniversary for the 20th anniversary of the coming into force of the Law for equality between men and women in Switzerland “*Egalité des droits - égalité réelle?* (Equality in rights – Real equality?)”¹⁶ was organised by the Equal Opportunities Office of the UNIL and the CEG, with the support of PlaGe, the NCCR LIVES, the GARCIA project and the Equal Opportunities Office of the EPFL (the Lausanne engineering school, which shares the same campus as the UNIL). After a theatrical presentation, two round tables brought together a former President of Switzerland (Ruth Dreifuss), the UNIL Rector and other personalities from the political and academic fields. The first round table was chaired by Farinaz Fassa and the concluding talk on equality in higher education was given by Nicky Le Feuvre.

¹² <https://www.gendercampus.ch/en/hochschulen/netzwerke/netzwerk-gender-studies-schweiz/forschungswerkstatt-2015> [retrieved 24 June 2016].

¹³ <https://www.gendercampus.ch/fr/hochschulen/netzwerke/netzwerk-gender-studies-schweiz/forschungswerkstatt-2015> [retrieved 24 June 2016].

¹⁴ <https://www.unil.ch/getactu/wwwplage/1456848520797/> [retrieved 24 June 2016].

¹⁵ <https://www.unil.ch/getactu/wwwssp/1458925550629/> [retrieved 24 June 2016].

¹⁶ <http://www.unil.ch/egalite/home/menuinst/programmes-et-activites/evenements/20-ans-leg-14062016.html> [retrieved 24 June 2016].

Roundtable chaired by Farinaz Fassa
© Audrey Mouton

Roundtable participants
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Concluding talk by Nicky Le Feuvre
© Marta Roca i Escoda

- The Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF) held a conference on “Gender and Excellence: Challenges in Research Funding II”¹⁷ on 20 June 2016 in Bern. Two panels were organised, on “Gender bias in the perception of excellence” and “Gender perspectives in research”. Nicky Le Feuvre was invited to chair the second panel, which investigated to what extent gender analysis needs to be better integrated into scientific research in the STEM disciplines.

5.1.4 Tools available to integrate gender in research and teaching

Several on-line tools for teachers and researchers to integrate gender into their activities were already available or under construction as we started with the GARCIA project. For example:

- At the UNIL, under the direction of the Vice-Rector in charge of “Junior Faculty Development and Diversity”, a toolbox entitled “Increasing inclusion in higher education: Tips and tools for teachers”¹⁸ was developed in 2014. Several workshops and conferences were also organised in 2013 and 2014 on the topic “Make your classroom inclusive: Workshop for teachers”. Gender is seen here as one element of the diversity of persons and topics that can be integrated in teaching.

¹⁷ <http://www.snf.ch/en/researchinFocus/newsroom/Pages/news-160427-snsf-conference-on-gender-and-excellence.aspx> [retrieved 24 June 2016].

¹⁸ <https://www.unil.ch/diversite/en/home/menuinst/ateliers-diversite.html> [retrieved 24 June 2016].

- The “e-equal+” project of the University of Fribourg entitled “Evaluation of teaching to favour gender equality”¹⁹ was financed by the Federal Gender Equality in Academia Programme for 2010-2013 and received the support of the University’s Rector’s Office. “The project promotes teachers’ awareness of gender issues in order to improve the quality of education working both at individual and institutional level. Designing new gender-related modules for the university’s training programme Did@cTIC and elaborating a self-evaluation questionnaire on gender issues in teaching are concrete elements implemented throughout the programme. At the institutional level, changes introduced have been accepted, recognised and supported by the different departments involved in the project. Nevertheless extending gender issues in teaching for most of the academic staff requires further efforts” (Rossier et al., 2010: English abstract). Following on a first project “e-equal” (2008-2010) entitled “*Enseignement, genre, qualité* (Teaching, gender, quality)”, it is at the crossroads of university didactics, equal opportunities and quality assurance. It aims at developing the quality of higher education teaching by integrating the gender perspective.
- The University of Applied Sciences and Arts Western Switzerland (HES-SO), has developed a “*Boîte à outils genre. Et si j’intégrais la perspective genre dans mon domaine?* (Gender Toolkit. And what if I integrated the gender perspective in my field?)”.²⁰ The aims of this toolkit are to disseminate gender studies throughout the HES-SO; to devise tools to introduce gender in teaching and research; to provide resources on gender studies for students; to support the equality and diversity policy inside the HES-SO.

Some other workshops addressing issues related to gender and gender studies have been organised, for example:

- The workshops on “How to use the epicene language” organised by the Equal opportunities office (11 March 2016; 15 April 2016; 20 May 2016). Their aim was to sensitise webmasters, heads of department, administrative teams of the deanships, communication officers, etc., to the use of gender-sensitive writing (“epicene” language). Sabine Kradolfer attended one of these workshops and she will disseminate information and support the implementation of epicene language in the NCCR LIVES. A Guidebook on gender sensitive language is available through the UNIL Equality Office web site.²¹

¹⁹ <http://www.unifr.ch/didactic/fr/recherche/projet-e-equal2> [retrieved 24 June 2016].

²⁰ <http://www.hes-so.ch/fr/vous-ouvrez-boite-outils-genre-bonne-recherche-6700.html> [retrieved 24 June 2016].

²¹ <https://www.unil.ch/egalite/home/menuinst/publications.html> [retrieved 24 June 2016].

5.2 Course materials

We decided to outsource the GARCIA workshops to gender studies specialists who could address the topic of gender in qualitative and quantitative methodologies for social scientists for the first workshop and in quantitative methodologies especially for psychologists and socio-psychologists for the second one.

As information on vertical and horizontal segregation is disseminated by the Equal Opportunities Office, and diversity conferences were organised by the Rectorate in charge of “Junior Faculty Development and Diversity”, we decided to focus our workshops on the design of gender-sensitive research contents with a particular focus on the methodological tools used in SSH research fields. Therefore, information on diversity (in the sense of ethnicity, race, mother tongue, class and gender), hierarchical gendered relations, different working conditions, allocation of resources, gender imbalance in teams, classrooms, etc., were not addressed in our workshops, so as to enable the workshop leaders to concentrate on methodology issues. Nevertheless, these topics could be interesting to discuss during workshops in our STEM department where gender awareness is lower and gender imbalance stronger (as already said, this kind of workshop could be organised in the second half of 2016, if we find a way to collaborate with the people in charge of the training to integrate gender-sensitive approaches in teaching and research in the STEM Faculty). In our SSH department, junior researchers (we were unable to persuade any senior researchers or professors to attend) and women (we had a large majority of women attending our workshop) are already aware of these kinds of inequalities.

5.2.1 Workshop 1 “Integrating gender in qualitative and quantitative research methods”

This one-day workshop was divided into a qualitative part given by Armelle Testenoire, a sociologist from the University of Rouen, in France, and a quantitative part given by Lavinia Gianettoni, a Senior Lecturer in social-psychology from the UNIL.

Armelle Testenoire focused her talk on the effects gender can have in qualitative research in life-course studies. She explained how gender and class are entwined and the difficulties that researchers can encounter in trying to disentangle them. She showed the effects of the sex of the interviewer in the interaction with the interviewee and how to set up devices capable of detecting the specific effects of gender. Drawing on her own research conducted through compared life stories of the two members of couples, she showed the value of this methodological device, which brings to light in particular the way that the gender vision structures the experiences of women and men, the selectivity of their memories and their subjective accounts of events.

Lavinia Gianettoni invited the participants to think about the use of quantitative methodology (and in particular surveys) for research with a gender perspective. She critically interrogated methods based on a traditional positivist logic and reflected on the way in which standardised surveys can contribute to the analysis of the processes of (re)production of gender inequalities. She paid particular attention to the construction

and purposes of gendered indicators (for more information, see the flyer in French in Appendix 1).

5.2.2 Workshop 2 “Quantitative methods under a gender lens”

In this workshop, Annalisa Casini, a social-psychologist at the Catholic University of Louvain in Belgium, took a participative approach. First, starting from her own research, she showed that comparing men and women does not mean that a gender-sensitive approach is reached. Therefore, she focused her reflections (1) on the fact that measuring gender at an individual level can be done in different ways (gender identity, internalisation of norms, adherence to gender norms, etc.); and (2) on the different ways to compare the “masculine” and the “feminine” by taking the sexual division of society into account. In the second part of the workshop, participants could work on their own data in a critical way and they tried to identify gender bias in the scales of measurement which are used by social-psychologists (for more information, see the flyer in French in Appendix 2).

5.3 Existing practices

The participants in our workshops were already gender-sensitive, as are most of the people who attend the events organised by the Equal Opportunities Office and other actions, conference, workshops, training courses, etc., on Gender Studies or equal opportunities, as explained by a participant: “Before the training event I already knew that the gender approach would be useful (otherwise I wouldn’t have attended)”.

We were relatively unsuccessful in attracting people who don’t consider themselves as Gender Studies specialists to these events. Although this could be seen as a lack of interest in gender issues on the part of our social science colleagues, it also reflects the relatively high level of institutionalisation of Gender Studies in the Swiss context. As a relatively autonomous field of scientific enquiry, this topic is considered to require specialist research knowledge and methods and is not seen as something that any social science researcher can claim as a specialist field.

5.4 Challenges

If we bear in mind that the 180 members of the NCCR LIVES and the 150 staff of the Social Sciences Institute are already very familiar with gender issues and that some of them use gender-sensitive methods in their own research, it proved to be quite difficult to attract participants for workshops on gender-sensitive issues. Either our colleagues felt that they were already gender specialists in their own right (having published widely on this issue, for example), or they believed that they had good reason not to be interested in developing a gender perspective (having already developed a theoretical critique of specific gender theories, for example).

In the end, our events were attended by an equal balance of NCCR LIVES members and non-members (8+8).

Our most important challenge would be to attract senior male researchers to our workshop and to raise awareness regarding gender-sensitive approaches amongst young researchers. We know that such persons are reluctant to attend this kind of workshop, sometimes because paradoxically they think they are already gender-sensitive and do not need any such training. One female colleague told us once that she had offered to organise a gender-sensitive training event for a hiring committee as she thought men were unsensitised to gender equality. A male colleague (among the most unsensitised), responded: "If you think you need such training, of course we could organise it. For me it won't be necessary".

We should also note that there is some resistance amongst Gender Studies specialists in the Swiss context to the idea that they should also be involved in promoting gender equality measures within the UNIL. With the progressive institutionalisation of Gender Studies as a relatively autonomous field of academic enquiry, we can observe an increasing hiatus between the issues and research topics that are taken up by Gender Studies specialists and those issues and topics that are of most interest to the academic Equality Offices. We believe that this is an issue that is probably not so important in countries or contexts where both gender studies and equal opportunities are still struggling for institutional recognition and resources (Le Feuvre & Andriocci, 2005).

5.5 Evaluation

We sent an on-line survey to the 16 participants in our two workshops in SSH asking the questions on the GARCIA evaluation form.

- To what extent you find gender relevant for your research?
- Did this workshop change your perspective on that? If so, how?
- To what extent do you find suggestions for gender-sensitive approaches applicable to your work?
- Is it feasible for you to apply these suggestions in one of your next research projects?

We received 12 answers (10 women and 2 men), but as 2 persons attended both workshops, only 2 persons did not answer the survey.

5.5.1 *To what extent you find gender relevant for your research?*

Nine participants answered this question and eight said that they are either working on gender or on comparisons between men and women in their research. One person answered more generally that: "Gender is an important dimension in all research (especially on vulnerability) and it seems useful to bear it in mind in doing quantitative analyses, whatever the topic of the research (even if it doesn't directly concern gender)."

5.5.2 Did this workshop change your perspective on that? If so, how? And to what extent do you find suggestions for gender-sensitive approaches applicable to your work?

As already said, the workshops were attended by persons already sensitive to gender issues and they did not change their point of view but got more accurate information on how to deal with gender issues in their research. The participants already use gender approaches and are convinced of their importance for doing good research. Participants therefore stated, for example: “The theory was useful to me in seeing how gender can be operationalised”; “Using biological sex categories isn’t the only approach that can be used”; “This workshop didn’t really make me change my mind about the usefulness of the gender approach but it did open up possible fields for the analysis of gender and the way gender can be conceptualised in research”.

One participant wrote that there are fields (family, work, health issues) where integrating gender seems to be easier than in others (without saying which fields these were), where the gender dimension has never been taken in account nor conceptualised any further than through a binary comparison between men and women.

A social-psychologist was really happy at the end of the second workshop, because for the first time she had the impression that she got deeper insight into the scales and other tools that are used on a daily basis in her discipline, and that the workshop provided – for the first time – something other than the “traditional” discourse on gender.

5.5.3 Is it feasible that you would apply these suggestions in one of your next research projects?

We received interesting answers to this question, as for example:

- “I had planned to do dyadic interviews before attending the workshop, so the workshop helped me on the one hand to extend my theoretical knowledge on dyadic interviews with couples and on the other hand gave me concrete examples of how to conduct the interviews (to separate a sample according to sex, to explore the male and female perspectives, to have two separate narratives of the [themes of her research] experience)”
- “I shall be attentive:
 - to the formulation of items in drawing up a questionnaire;
 - to the fact that a question may be interpreted differently depending on the sex of the person who is answering;
 - to reading and analysing gender not only as a marker of men/women differences but also at the level of attitudes/behaviours which may be more masculine/feminine, and considering gender relations as an organising principle of society.”

5.6 References

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Appendix 1

PROGRAMME DOCTORAL – 2 NOVEMBRE 2015

INTÉGRER LE GENRE DANS LES DISPOSITIFS DE RECHERCHE QUALITATIFS ET QUANTITATIFS

ATELIER ORGANISÉ EN COLLABORATION ENTRE LE PROGRAMME DOCTORAL LIVES ET LE SECTEUR ÉGALITÉ DE LIVES.

Informations générales

Date : 2 novembre 2015

Lieu : Université de Lausanne

Bâtiment Amphipôle

Salle 315.1

1015 Lausanne

Frais : Les frais de participation, de transport et les repas des participant-e-s inscrit-e-s sont prise en charge par le PRN LIVES. Les frais de transports sont remboursés sur la base du tarif CFF en 2^e classe.

Armelle Testenoire - Repérer les rapports de genre lors du recueil et de l'analyse de récits de vie

L'objectif de cette demi-journée est d'identifier l'effet des rapports de genre lors de la réalisation de recherches qualitative portant sur les parcours de vie. Un premier temps sera consacré à l'analyse de l'imbrication des rapports de genre et de classe et des difficultés à identifier leurs effets respectifs. La réflexion portera ensuite sur les effets de la situation d'enquête, en particulier le sexe de l'enquêtrice, et la mise en place de dispositifs susceptibles de cerner les effets spécifiques du genre. L'analyse s'appuiera sur des enquêtes menées par récits de vie croisés auprès des deux membres d'un même couple pour mettre en évidence l'intérêt de ce dispositif méthodologique. Il permet notamment de mettre en évidence la manière dont la division sexuée structure les expériences des femmes et des hommes, la sélectivité de leur mémoire ainsi que leur expressivité.

Lavinia Gianettoni - Indicateurs de genre dans les enquêtes.

L'objectif de cette demi-journée est de réfléchir à l'utilisation des méthodes quantitative, et plus particulièrement des enquêtes par questionnaire, lorsque l'on réalise des recherches dans une perspective de genre. Nous allons aborder cette question en partant du présupposé d'une complémentarité entre approches quantitatives et qualitatives. Tout en adoptant une attitude critique vis-à-vis des méthodes basées sur une logique positiviste traditionnelle, il s'agira de réfléchir à la manière dont des instruments tels que les enquêtes par questionnaires standardisés peuvent contribuer à l'analyse des processus de (re)production des inégalités entre les sexes. Une attention particulière sera accordée aux procédures de construction d'indicateurs de genre et à leurs finalités.

La deuxième partie du cours sera dédiée à des illustrations pratiques de construction d'indicateurs de genre visant à dénaturaliser les catégories de sexe. Nous travaillerons sur des bases de données qui abordent deux thématiques distinctes : l'imbrication du sexisme et du racisme (données MosaïCH), et la transgression des normes de genre dans les trajectoires de formation (données TREE, TRansition entre l'École et l'Emploi). Un des objectifs de cette deuxième partie est d'aboutir à des discussions avec les participant-e-s sur la potentielle utilité des enquêtes existantes pour leurs propres travaux, ainsi que sur les limites de ces instruments et la nécessité de les articuler avec d'autres méthodes, notamment qualitatives.

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Les Pôles de recherche nationaux (PRN) sont un instrument d'encouragement du Fonds National de la Recherche Scientifique

Programme, 2 novembre, 2015 (Bâtiment Amphipôle, Salle 315.1)

08.45 - 9.00 : Café d'accueil

09.00 - 10.30 : Intervention d'Armelle Testenoire (1ère partie)

10.30 - 11.00 : Pause-café

11.00 - 12.30 : Intervention d'Armelle Testenoire (2ème partie)

12.30 - 14.00 : Repas en commun

14.00 - 15.30 : Intervention de Lavinia Gianettoni (1ère partie) : Présentation des enjeux liés à l'adoption d'une perspective de genre dans l'analyse des données d'enquête

15.30 - 16.00 : Pause-café

16.00 - 17.30 : Intervention de Lavinia Gianettoni (2ème partie) : Exemples tirés des données d'enquête (MosaïCH, TREE) et discussions avec les participant-e-s.

Intervenantes :

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Lavinia Gianettoni, ISS et PRN LIVES, Université de Lausanne

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Liste des participant-e-s

Appendix 2

DOMAINE ÉGALITÉ

FORMATIONS EN ÉTUDES GENRE DU PRN LIVES

ATELIER

“LES ANALYSES QUANTITATIVES À L'ÉPREUVE DE LA PERSPECTIVE GENRE”

Organisé par le domaine égalité du NCCR LIVES et le projet européen de recherche GARCIA

Conférencière invitée : Professeure Annalisa Casini

Université de Lausanne, Bâtiment Géopolis, Salle 5313, 1015 Lausanne

Plan d'accès : <http://www.unil.ch/acces/en/home/menuguid/planete-unil.html>

25 avril 2016

13.30-17.00

If english-speaking colleagues of the NCCR LIVES would like to take part in this workshop, the speaker has agreed to give her talk in English, on request.

La participation à cet atelier est libre, mais pour des raisons d'organisation, l'inscription est obligatoire avant le 20 avril 2016. Des lectures de cadrage vous seront fournies avant l'atelier. Les inscriptions seront prises dans leur ordre d'arrivée mais priorité sera donnée aux membres du PNR LIVES.

Organisation

- Domaine égalité, PRN LIVES (Farinaz Fassa & Sabine Kradolfer)
- Projet européen de recherche GARCIA : <http://garciaproject.eu/>

Pour vous inscrire, recevoir les lectures de cadrage et pour toute question, veuillez prendre contact avec la responsable égalité du PRN :

Sabine Kradolfer, Sabine.KradolferMorales@unil.ch

Université de Lausanne | Bâtiment Géopolis | CH-1015 Lausanne | T +41 21 692 38 51 | equality@lives-nccr.ch

Les Pôles de recherche nationaux (PRN) sont un instrument d'encouragement du Fonds National de la Recherche Scientifique

Descriptif

Cet atelier, fortement interactif, s'articulera autour de deux moments distincts. D'abord, en partant de ses recherches et du postulat que comparer hommes et femmes ne signifie pas « faire une analyse de genre », la conférencière amènera quelques réflexions sur 1) les différentes manières de « mesurer le genre » au niveau individuel (par ex. identité de genre, adhésion aux normes de genre, intériorisation des normes, self-construal, etc.) et sur 2) les manières de comparer le « masculin » et le « féminin » en tenant compte de la division sexuelle de la société et des effets produits. Ensuite, les participant-e-s seront invité-e-s à repenser/retravailler collectivement leurs propres données à la lumière des réflexions précédentes, en adoptant une posture critique quant à d'éventuels biais de genre des échelles de mesure qu'ils et elles utilisent dans leur quotidien de recherche.

Conférencière: Annalisa Casini

Annalisa Casini est Docteure en psychologie. Elle enseigne la psychologie du travail et de la santé au travail à l'Université catholique de Louvain (UCL) où elle fait partie du Laboratoire de Psychologie du travail (WOP Lab) du Centre pour l'Étude du Comportement Social (CECoS) et du Centre Interdisciplinaire de Recherche Travail, État et Société (CIRTES). Ses intérêts de recherche portent sur les liens entre genre, travail et bien-être de travailleurs et travailleuses avec une attention particulière aux dynamiques de reconnaissance professionnelle. Par le passé, elle a travaillé sur les stratégies identitaires impliquées dans le phénomène du 'plafond de verre' et sur celles de la mobilité sociale et du changement social, particulièrement en ce qui concerne les femmes. Elle coordonne depuis 2005 le cycle de conférences *Atelier Genre(s) et Sexualité(s)* : (<http://www.ulb.ac.be/igs/lags/>).

Sélection de références bibliographiques en lien avec le thème de l'atelier

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6. SLOVENIA

By Jovana Mihajlović Trbovc

6.1 Introduction

In Slovenian academic sphere, in general, there is no widespread practice of including gender into research, unless the topic is specifically dealing with gender as such. This is the rule also at two Slovenian test institutions, namely: the Department for Agronomy of the Biotechnical Faculty, the University of Ljubljana (example from STEM), and the Fran Ramovš Institute of the Slovenian Language, the Research Centre of the Slovenian Academy of Sciences and Arts (example from SSH). Therefore, the workshop on integrating gender perspective into research had to start from the basics. Firstly, by posing the question: 'Why do we need gender in research?' And secondly, by building up to more sophisticated issues of how to integrate gender in academic practice.

The workshops were not envisioned as a lecture or training, but rather as an exercise in posing questions which should raise awareness on the importance of gender-sensitive approach, regardless of the discipline. The workshop outline follows the structure of the 'Recommendations,' from the *Toolkit for Integrating Gender-Sensitive Approach into Research and Teaching*, created within GARCIA project by the members of the Slovenian team.¹ The Toolkit was created to be generic and applicable to the widest possible range of sciences and humanities, hence the workshop based on it was not aiming at 'delivering knowledge', but rather at raising a discussion. The method of the workshop is presented in detail in section Two of this Report.

In order to test to what extent interactive model of the workshop works in practice, Slovenian GARCIA team organised a pilot workshop for the employees of the Jovan Hadži Institute of Biology and Institute of Slovenian Literature and Literary Studies, which are both part of the Research Centre of the Slovenian Academy of Sciences and Arts. The pilot workshop took place on the premises of the Research Centre on 1st March 2016, and lasted for 3 hours with a break for a snack. It was led by the co-author of the *Toolkit for Integrating Gender-Sensitive Approach*, Dr. Jovana Mihajlović Trbovc, while the other co-author, Dr. Ana Hofman, participated in the discussion and took ethnographic notes.

While all employees were invited, the attendance rate for the Institute of Biology was 50% (1 female and 6 male participants) and 25% for Literary Studies (1 female and 2 male participants). Compared to the overall gender structure of the two institutes, we can conclude that from the Institute of Biology, 25% of female researchers (1 out of 4) and 60% of male researchers (6 out of 10) attended the workshop, whereas in case of the Institute of Literary Studies, 25% of both male and female researchers attended the workshop.

The pilot study proved that the workshop model works in practice, but it also brought some substantial insights. It became evident that the academics not familiar with gender

¹ See Jovana Mihajlović Trbovc and Ana Hofman, 'Toolkit for Integrating Gender-Sensitive Approach into Research and Teaching,' GARCIA Working paper 6, pp. 25-38. Available at: http://garciaproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2015/12/GARCIA_working_paper_6.pdf.

studies related much more strongly to the concept of 'diversity' than gender. Thus it proved more effective to present how gender balance contributes the quality of research through laying out how diversity (understood as ethnicity, class, mother tongue, etc. *and* gender) enriches research conduct and should be considered when presenting results to the general audience.

Since the *Toolkit for Integrating Gender-Sensitive Approach into Research and Teaching* has been published in November 2015, it has been translated into the Slovenian language, adjusted and published both in print and online, with a free access.² Thus, it has been presented during workshops at both STEM and SSH test institutions, and disseminated among their staff. The two workshops took place on 20th June (the Institute of the Slovenian Language) and on 21st June 2016 (Department of Agronomy). The first workshop was organised in the same place and in the same manner as the pilot workshop. The only addition was that Dr. Tanja Petrović, another GARCIA team member, participated in the discussion with the researchers from the Language Institute, contributing with her linguistic expertise. Only 12.5% of the full-time employed academic staff attended.³ Compared to the gender structure of the Institute as a whole, it means that 14.8% of female researchers (4 out of 27) and 7.7% of male ones (1 out of 13) attended the workshop.

The Department of Agronomy at the Biotechnical Faculty is not a primary institution for the majority of the GARCIA team members, and as a test institution, it is external to Slovenian GARCIA project partner, being outside its direct influence. Bearing in mind previous resistance at the Agronomy Department towards activities aimed at reflecting on the issues of gender,⁴ we decided to invite an international expert who has extensive experience in conducting gender-related workshops for agriculture researchers – Dr. Sandra Lee Russo. She adjusted the already developed workshop template, introducing some methods of her own, which will be further described in section Two of this Report. The invitations to the workshop were first sent out only to the employees of the Department of Agronomy, and then upon the meagre response rate, we extended the invitation to all the employees of the Biotechnology Faculty. Furthermore, the colleague who had previously conducted individual interviews with some staff members at the test Department (within the WP6) sent them personal reminders, while the workshop was announced through posters throughout the building. In spite of that, only two young female researchers attended the workshop. While the infinitesimally small attendance rate was explained away by the head of the Department as resulting from staff's other obligations, it undoubtedly reflects the academics' lack of interest in the topic of the workshop.

Paradoxically (or indicatively), the greatest challenge was to make test institutions cooperate in organising the workshops. In both cases, the institutional resistance was reflected in the attitude of the heads of the Department and Institute, regardless of gender. The individuals at the leading positions (a female and male, respectively) did not

² Available at: <http://zalozba.zrc-sazu.si/sl/publikacije/prirocnik-za-uvajanje-spolno-obcutljivega-pristopa-v-raziskovanje-in-poucevanje#v>.

³ We counted only the staff that is employed full-time (not those working on partial contracts), and excluded technical and support staff, since they would not be expected to attend the workshop designed for researchers only.

⁴ Such a resistance was evident during the research conducted for work-package 7 (on the gap between the formal and actual selection criteria for early career academics).

perceive the workshop on gender-related issues as an event they should help organising. While they did enable the workshop to take place, they showed lack of personal interest and agency in promoting attendance among the staff, rather regarding it as unwanted.

On the other hand, the researchers attending the workshop in average displayed significantly less resistance than their supervisors. Those who expressed a certain level of scepticism showed mistrust with regard to how to apply the suggestions laid out in the workshop, but were not resistant to the whole idea. These noted challenges will be described in section Four of this Report.

The Report concludes with the summary of the evaluation reports filled out by the attendants of the workshop, and suggestions for future activities integrating gender perspective into research and curricula.

6.2 Course materials used at the workshops

The workshop entitled 'The Role of Gender in Research' was comprised of PRESENTATIONS and ACTIVITIES. Presentations were given by the workshop leader, outlining the argumentation of why and how gender is relevant for academic working environment, in envisioning a research project, posing research questions, choosing and applying methodologies, designing and presenting research results, and what role it plays in teaching. In between the presentations, Activities were organised as clusters of questions posed to the workshop participants who were invited to respond based on their own experiences and reflect on them. By the rule, a discussion ensued, which was moderated and guided by the workshop leader. The topics of the Presentations and Activities were following successive segments of the 'Recommendations' from the *Toolkit for Integrating Gender-Sensitive Approach into Research and Teaching*.

It should be noted that all Institutes at the Research Centre of the Slovenian Academy of Sciences and Arts of which employees attended workshops work predominantly in research, while only a few of them engage in teaching as a side-job. Thus, those workshops spent more time on research-related than curricula-related topics. Here, we are presenting a general structure of Presentations and Activities, and bringing some of the illustrative examples of a gender-sensitive approach applied to particular disciplines to which researchers attending workshops belong, namely agronomy, biology, and linguistics and literature studies.

The first PRESENTATION of the workshops was related to the working environment in which a research is conducted. The workshop participants discussed gender ratios in their own Institutes and their Sections (e.g., the Institute of the Slovenian Language is organised into the Dialectological, Lexicological, Terminological Section and others). They were asked to consider to what extent their working teams are gender balanced, whether they noticed patterns of hierarchical gendered relations in working teams, and whether working their conditions discriminated against one particular gender.

As already mentioned in the Introduction, the pilot workshop demonstrated that it is easier to argue why gender balance in working teams is relevant if it is presented through benefits diversity (understood as ethnicity, class, mother tongue, etc. and gender) brings to working teams.

The pilot workshop © ZRC SAZU

The workshop leader opened the issue of hierarchical gendered relations by providing the most typical example: a senior researcher in the position of power to control research funds is male, while female junior researchers do most of the administrative and 'invisible' work of the project. The discussions among the participants revealed that this is the most burning issue for young female academics, except in the case of the Institute of the Slovenian Language, where the majority of the staff is female.

The workshop then tackled the issues of introducing gender into the content of research. This section opened with ACTIVITY in which all participants were asked to make a mental experiment; they had to imagine one of their projects that is most related to humans and/or society, and outline the answers to the following questions on a piece of paper:

- What was the project's main research question?
- What methodologies were used in the project?
- What (human-related) data were collected within the project?
- What were the results of the project (excluding academic publications)?
- Who benefited from the project?

The participants were required to keep the paper throughout the training as a reminder, since later Activities pondered into each of these questions by asking participants to reflect on the exemplary project of their own.

The PRESENTATION on posing gender-sensitive research questions explained that gender-sensitive approach subsumes that we take into consideration differences between men and women during the very conception of the initial idea. Depending on how a particular project tackles human lives, these differences may range from biological differences, different lived experiences, to different social expectations put on men and women.

The workshop leader presented the following example of a project conducted at the Department of Agronomy: An agronomy research project deals with trends in the development of small-scale farming in Slovenia (e.g., changing the economic situation in Europe, opting for bio/eco-farming, etc.). Although the project did have elements of gender-sensitivity, a complete integration of gender into such a project would pose questions of how changes in the social position of women (socio-political emancipation) influenced traditional decision making within a farming family. For instance, do female

farm-owners behave differently compared to male ones (e.g., are they more inclined to opt for bio/eco-farming)?

The subsequent ACTIVITY asked participants to think about their exemplary research project (a mental experiment) and reflect on whether they had both men and women in mind when formulating the research question. Further questions were:

- What do you think now? – How do men and women differently relate to your research problem?
- How could this be reflected in a new/modified research question?

These questions by rule incited discussion among the workshop participants.

At the Department of Agronomy, this example stimulated one of the workshop participants to lay out a project she has been coordinating in the past year. That project promotes aquaponics as a new technique of small plant production⁵ and helps pilot farms to run it. The researcher presented how she noted that female farmers responded differently to the introduction of the new technology. This incited discussion among the workshop attendees (both agriculture and social science experts) about how the raised issue relates to structural characteristics of Slovenian agriculture. The discussion led to practical suggestions on how the project could be adjusted to integrate gender dimension systematically throughout the project, from its practical implementation to final analytical findings as scientific results of the project.

At the workshop with the researchers from the Institute of the Slovenian Language, the workshop leader was challenged to respond what a gender-sensitive approach would be in the case of research topics 'where there is no gender.' Such is the case of 19th century Slovenian literature, the workshop attendee claimed, asking: 'When there are no female authors, how can you put them into a literary anthology?' The response of the workshop leader was that precisely the lack of female authors should be one of the topics raised and problematized in the introduction of such an anthology, which usually gives some social and historical context in which particular literary pieces were written. Furthermore, a gender-sensitive approach would also analyse how gender roles are presented and projected in the given literature. Finally, such an approach might lead to digging out some female authors who did write during 19th century, but were not considered as a part of the literary canon, or were ignored by previous anthologies.

This discussion was a suitable prelude to the PRESENTATION on potential traps of essentialising differences between males and females, which leads to reproduction of gender stereotypes. It raised the question to the researchers of whether they might be (unintentionally) projecting stereotypical roles onto how women and men would behave, what they need and desire. This question raised a particularly vibrant debate among the biologists attending the workshop. It revealed that zoology researchers, when intending to include gender perspective into their research, sometimes tend to project the humanised notion of gender onto explaining different behaviours (e.g., in reproduction) of species.

⁵ Aquaponics in this case refers to a system that combines fish breeding tanks (aquariums) with hydronic cultivation (growing plants using mineral nutrient solutions in water, without soil) of herbs in a symbiotic system.

The next PRESENTATION in the workshop described principles of a gender-sensitive methodology, and how it could be applied to methodologies that are used in the analysis of societal processes, policies, human populations (e.g. surveys), or in laboratory or medical experiments, to name a few. For biologists attending the workshop, an example from Belgian GARCIA project partner was given:⁶

A female biologist was working on the reproductive behaviour of a particular species of butterflies. While conducting literature review, she noticed that previous studies recorded the male butterfly behaviour as being decisive for the reproductive habits or frequencies. However, while conducting her own experiments, she realised that the average size of the female butterfly was much larger than the male one, and that the environment of the experiment mattered in terms of how free in space female butterflies were in order to increase reproductive behaviour. In fact, she determined that there was a bias in butterfly research pertaining to male butterfly predominance in determining reproductive behaviour in most literature, written majorly by male researchers.

The relating ACTIVITY invited participants to think about their exemplary research project (a mental experiment) and answer the following questions:

- Was your methodology gender-sensitive in any aspect?
- How would you modify it, so that it would be more gender-sensitive?
- How would you design methodology, so that you would get gender-sensitive data?

These questions raised a particularly vibrant debate among linguists attending the workshop, some of whom nurtured a very narrow understanding of the role of gender in their research – only as grammatical gender. This led a linguistic expert of GARCIA team to provide the following example:

In dialectology, the notion of the ideal, authentic speaker is gendered, as women are usually seen as ideal subjects for dialectological research; women are perceived as uneducated and immobile, so their chances of exposure to standard language or other vernaculars are reduced to a minimum. Such a construction is ideological and ignores a great diversity of women's experiences and the fact that these experiences are often characterised by mobility and hybridity in language practices.

A similar example was presented by another GARCIA team member who comes from the field of ethno-musicology, which traditionally perceives women as a socially less-mobile subject, who are thus able to transmit the traditional knowledge (music). Another flawed gendered assumption of traditional ethno-musicology is that women are transmitters of traditional music, but not its authors – reproducing the stereotype that women know how to preserve knowledge, but have no ability to create new knowledge (music).

The next PRESENTATION tackled the issue of gender-sensitive language. In Slovenian, as in most European languages, the plural masculine form is often used to refer to both men and women – when referring to unknown individuals, officials' titles, names of

⁶ See Ana Hofman and Jovana Mihajlović Trbovc, eds., 'Gender Dimension in Research and Curriculum: 12 SSH and STEM test institutions,' GARCIA working paper 7, p. 78. Available at: http://garciaproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2015/12/GARCIA_working_paper_7.pdf.

professions, etc. The use of the feminine form, or the interchanging of masculine and feminine ones, makes women more visible in both life and science.

The junior female agronomy researcher attending the workshop has instantly recognised this issue. She noted that even though agronomy as science became increasingly feminised in last 20 years in Slovenia, female academics in this field are still referring to themselves in the masculine form of the professional title (*agronom*) and not in its feminine counterpart (*agronomka*). While commenting that she, personally, has not pondered on the issue before, she would consider using the female form in the future.

The final workshop PRESENTATION posed the question of how to produce gender-sensitive results in a research project. It incited researchers towards thinking about project beneficiaries and users of project results from a gendered perspective. The subsequent ACTIVITY made participants think about their exemplary research project (a mental experiment) yet again, asking them how they would modify the project, so that it would produce gender-sensitive results.

Since this sounded particularly abstract to linguists attending the workshop, the workshop leader drew attention to the role of language in constructing and representing gender. In order to demonstrate how language can play an active role in the symbolic positioning of women as inferior to men, she offered the example of 'asymmetries between pairs of gender-differentiated terms, where the female term has negative connotations, while the male term is either neutral or positive.'⁷ The example of words 'master' and 'mistress' in the English language illustrates how 'female terms may start on an equal footing, but become devalued over time.'⁸ Initially, both words referred to persons having power, authority, or ownership, but over time, the feminine version 'mistress' became a derogatory term with sexual connotations. The researchers participating in the workshop recognised the same phenomenon in the Slovenian language, with a bulk of terms that mark women as deviant or deficient, and without masculine counterparts of the terms. A vibrant discussion ensued on the topic of how to deal with such an issue in the strict minimalistic form of a dictionary, thesaurus or lexicon, as the primary result of projects the researchers were involved in.

The common pattern of all three conducted workshops was that the discussions among attending researchers broke the limits of the designated time and continued in informal settings after the official end of the workshops.

6.3 Existing practices

In the Report that mapped gender dimension in the existing research and curricula in test institutions conducted by Slovenian GARCIA partner, it has been noted that gender is not systematically integrated as a part of academic practice. However, a large majority of the researchers evaluate themselves as being gender-sensitive. At the beginning of each workshop, attendants were asked to fill out a simple self-evaluation form, which posed the following questions, offering YES and NO answers:

⁷ Suzanne Romaine, 'Language and Gender' in Encyclopaedia of Life Support Systems, <http://www.eolss.net/sample-chapters/c04/e6-20b-09-01.pdf>.

⁸ Ibid.

- Do you find yourself to be gender-sensitive in your research?
- Thus far, have you integrated gender in any of your research projects?
- Have you ever used a gender-sensitive methodology?

The discussions during the workshops revealed that researchers usually understood 'gender-sensitivity' in a very narrow sense, as either 'the notification of sex when examining species' among biologists or 'the usage of grammatical gender' among linguists. Nevertheless, certain shifts towards more gender-sensitive conduct did take place in academic practice, even though researchers did not recognise it immediately as such. A good example are revisions of the standard dictionary of the Slovenian language, which have been conducted by the Institute of the Slovenian Language. The newly revised Dictionary of the Slovenian Standard Language (*Slovar slovenskega knjižnega jezika*) is including feminine versions of professions and titles as independent word units, while the previous version of the Dictionary mostly treated feminine terms only as derivatives of masculine forms.

The linguistic researchers attending the workshop also recalled discussions they were having in the course of their work on dictionaries and lexicons, which are aimed at 'being more politically correct'. Since the standard methodology requires them to define words on the basis of their usage in the collected corpus of texts (which includes popular literature, newspaper articles and other available publications), they expressed being troubled by sometimes finding 'offensive' and 'unsuitable' forms of word usages, implying derogatory meanings for women or sexual minorities. While the researchers did not use expressions as 'sexism' or 'patriarchy,' these were the phenomenon they had trouble dealing with. The linguists expressed awareness that the actual usage of some words is problematic, but were also firm on the point that their role is to describe a variety of word usage in the living language, not to correct it. Therefore, they framed their aim in producing a new Dictionary in such a way that it would 'find balance' between a 'proper' description of words as dictionary units and their 'objective' usage in the linguistic corpus. They were reluctant to adopt idea that they may play an active role in reforming dominant sexist language.

The workshop at the Department of Agronomy is not representative of the analysis of the existing practices in the integration of gender into research conducted at this institution, due to an extremely low response rate of its academic staff. However, the researchers attending the workshop revealed that they were taking gender dimension in consideration in the course of the implementation of interdisciplinary projects in which they were involved, even when gender dimension was not a part of the initial research design. These interdisciplinary projects intertwine agronomy research and practice with different forms of social engagement (e.g., unemployed rural population or school dropouts). Without specific training in gender studies, the young female researchers intuitively recognised gendered relations within communities they were interacting with.

6.4 Noted challenges

As mentioned in the Introduction to this Report, the greatest challenge for this kind of workshop was getting support of the test institutions to organise it. In the case of both the Agronomy Department and the Institute of the Slovenian Language, it seemed as if the heads of the test institutions did not recognise how their Department/Institute will or could profit from a workshop on gender-related issues. It should be noted that these two institutions are associate partners in GARCIA projects, which does not bring any direct financial gain to them and partially clarifies the lack of engagement in organising workshops. In its endeavour to conduct the workshops, GARCIA team argued that the integration of a gender-sensitive approach would help research institutions in gaining the European Union funded grant schemes, which require the application of principles of gender equality.⁹ However, this long-term benefit was not recognised as such by the institutions' heads. This resistance was, to some extent, curbed in the case of the Institute of the Slovenian Language, which is a part of the larger Research Centre of the Slovenian Academy of Sciences and Arts, the Director of which is individually involved in the GARCIA project, and who was able to exercise relative pressure on the head of this particular Institute. In the case of the Department of Agronomy, which is a part of the Biotechnical Faculty of the University of Ljubljana, there were no means for a similar hierarchical pressure to comply with the overall aim of the GARCIA project.

The resistance to gender issues, common to many STEM institutions, was evident also among the individual academic staff of the Department of Agronomy. For instance, when GARCIA member team personally approached one of the female mid-level researchers at the Department, with whom she was privately acquainted, the researcher put her reasons for not attending the workshop in following terms: 'I'm not sure I would agree with the approach you are advocating. Women are sometimes greater enemies to other women.' Tacitly indicating that feminist approach may be counterproductive, she expressed mistrust of such a workshop, questioning whether it could be of any worth for her work. However, she implied a certain level of awareness of gender imbalance in the academic world by stating: 'This is a men's world, and each one of us females has to find her way of navigating within it.' Nevertheless, she did not recognise that it could be changed or even that it is unfair and unjust. To the extent that this kind of attitude is representative of the entire academic population in a particular discipline, the type of workshop described in this Report cannot transform such resistance. This type of workshop, aimed at raising awareness on gender-sensitivity in research, is effective only if participants actually *want* to attend them. In most cases, the very interest for participation in such a workshop is already indicative of at least minimum level of gender-sensitive awareness. Such a 'Catch-22' problem can only be solved by some sort of institutional determination to improve the level of gender equality and sensitivity to gender-related issues.

⁹ As indicated in European Commission documents, Science Policies in the European Union: *Promoting Excellence through Mainstreaming Gender Equality*. A Report from the ETAN Expert Group on Women and Science. European Commission, 2000. Available at: ftp://ftp.cordis.europa.eu/pub/improving/docs/g_wo_etan_en_200101.pdf; *Women and Science: Excellence and Innovation – Gender Equality in Science*. Commission Staff Working Document, Brussels 2005. Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/research/swafs/pdf/pub_gender_equality/sec_report_en.pdf.

6.5 Evaluation

At the end of each workshop, participants were required to fill out simple evaluation forms, which posed following questions:

- Did this workshop change your perspective on the relevance of gender in your research? If yes, how?
- To what extent do you find suggestions for a gender-sensitive approach applicable to your work?
- Is it feasible that you would apply these suggestions in one of your next research projects?

The majority of respondents declared that the workshop expanded their understanding of how gender could be related to their primary research topic, although it was framed differently among the researchers coming from different disciplines. For most biologists and agronomists the notion of gender as a social construction was a new concept. Biologists in particular were interested in gender relations within the academic working environment. A senior biological researcher stated, during the workshop, that he personally never paid attention to the gender of the authors he had been citing in his scientific papers, but stated he would pay more attention to 'who [he] would be quoting in the future' in order to make female authors more visible. A young female agronomist researcher stated that this workshop 'widened [her] perspective on [her] research,' making her even more aware of how gender is intertwined with her main research topic. Another young female agronomist stated that she 'finally learned proper words for things [she] already knew,' indicating the potential of this kind of workshops for spreading specific gender-related categorical apparatus outside humanities and social sciences.

The language studies and linguistics scholars were evenly divided among those who stated that the workshop made them more aware of the relevance of gender for their research and those who claimed that they were already familiar with the issues. Similarly, they were evenly divided among those who found the suggested gender-sensitive approach as applicable to their research conduct and those who did not see it as significantly relevant for their particular research topic. The first cluster had a common theme of recognising that they could apply a gender-sensitive methodology in the future. On the other hand, among biologists, even when they recognised the importance of taking gender into consideration, they were not sure if they would be able to apply a gender-sensitive approach to their own research. The most positive response was from the agronomist researchers who openly expressed that this workshop gave them ideas for future collaborative projects that would involve a gender dimension.

In several evaluation forms, the participants expressed (what has also been mentioned during the workshop discussions) that they felt enriched by a better understanding of how the academics from the 'opposing camp' of STEM-SSH divide perceived scientific problems from a different perspective. They recognised the need for a more interdisciplinary dialogue, and presumed that a gender-sensitive approach could be integrated into larger interdisciplinary projects.

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